

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR
D.5.5 PCP INVITATION TO TENDERS / REQUEST FOR TENDERS
TEMPLATE
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INTRODUCTION

LEA aims to contribute to the knowledge transfer, dialogue and awareness-raising of innovation procurement within the learning technology sector.

This document was produced within LEA's strategy of enhancing stakeholders' knowledge about the various phases of a PCP and PPI and their specific rules and documentation. The various public procurement laws and rules and its required documents might get away potentially interested parties, especially if we are referring to a not well-known procedure, as it is still the PCP and the PPI. This document was created to contribute to clarify and bring stakeholders closer to these procedures, so they feel more comfortable to take part in this type of processes. Specifically, this document addresses the PCP and focuses on one of the steps of "Phase 0" (see Figure 1), gathering useful information and guidelines to prepare a PCP Invitation to Tenders (ITT) / Request for Tender. The ITT presents the legal framework of a PCP, containing all the relevant and necessary information concerning the PCP (description of the services to be procured, available budget, timeline, conditions, etc.).

Figure 1: Main phases of procurement for innovation (PCP and PPI)

Fortunately, today, it is possible to find several resources containing useful information related to PCP in general, and PCP ITT documentation, in particular. This document reflects those multiple sources of information, as well as the discussions and lessons learned from LEA project. In specific, this document was designed based on:

- the guidance documentation provided by DG-CONNECT of the European Commission¹;
- “literature review” of implemented PCP ITT, namely IMAILE²;
- toolkit produced by EAFIP³;
- materials and discussions from LEA project.

Within LEA, a document with guidelines for drafting a PPI Invitation to Tender was also produced.

=> [LEA D5.4 ITT PPI](#)

The usefulness of this document lies, thus, not only on the provision of guidelines to prepare a PCP ITT, but also on the sharing of interesting and relevant sources of information, where the reader can find further (and, in some case, updated) details on this topic.

HOW DOES THIS DOCUMENT WORK?

- Instructions and footnotes **in blue** should be deleted.
- For options [in square brackets], choose the option that applies (options not chosen, and the brackets should be deleted).
- For fields in [grey in square brackets], enter the appropriate data (and remove the grey colour and the brackets).
- Examples are included in grey coloured boxes and national-specific references in **green**, **blue**, **yellow** and **orange** coloured boxes, to be adapted to the undertaken procurement.

Since PCP falls under the EU public procurement directives and national laws, possible templates provided by national entities should work. You can use this template as a checklist in order to cross-check the administrative requirements and provisions against the applicable national law.

This document is mainly designed for a joint tender ('joint PCP'), that is supposed to follow the national law applicable in the Lead Procurer's country. However,

¹ [EU Grants: H2020 Guidance — PCP procurement documents: V2.1 – 07.01.2020. Request for tenders.](#)

² <http://www.imaile.eu/>

³ <https://eafip.eu/toolkit/>

contents are provided to adapt this document into a coordinated tender ('coordinated PCP'), which should follow the different applicable national legal frameworks. Given the advantages and disadvantages of joint and coordinated PCPs, we encourage interested entities to develop joint PCP processes. Note that the lead procurer has a less prominent role for coordinated PCPs than for joint PCP. In the case of joint PCP, there is only one joint PCP request for tenders launched. In the case of coordinated PCPs, there are several separate PCP requests for tenders launched by the individual procurers in the buyer's group. The coloured boxes reflect, for certain contents and sections, the specific applicable rules in the countries interested by LEA PCP initiative (Italy, Finland, Portugal and Spain). Please double-check the instructions, to make sure they work for the selected procurement model.

WHAT IS JOINT AND COORDINATED PROCUREMENT?

Joint / coordinated procurement entails the combining of procurement actions of two or more public procurers from the same or from different countries. Joint / coordinated transnational procurement is when two or more public procurers from different countries combine procurement actions.

- **In coordinated procurement**, several procurers carry out together the preparation but not the execution of the procurement procedure. Procurers define together common requirements specifications and consult the market together on available solutions, but launch separate procurement procedures to buy separately the amount of products they each individually need.
- **In joint procurement**, several procurers carry out together not only the preparation but also the execution of the procurement procedure. Compared to coordinated procurement, there is only one joint procurement procedure launched.

Source: The EAFIP Toolkit: Module 2, pp. 136

LEARN MORE LEA Webinar 6: [Understanding the legal aspects of joined vs. coordinated innovation procurement](#), by Sara Bedin and Marta Coto

The document is updated to the date of 29th February 2019.

FIND MORE INFORMATION ON ITT DOCUMENTATION

**EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DG-CONNECT**

on public procurement for
innovation [>WEBSITE<](#)

DG-GROW

on public procurement
[>WEBSITE<](#)

**EAFIP - EUROPEAN
ASSISTANCE FOR
INNOVATION
PROCUREMENT INITIATIVE**

[>WEBSITE<](#)

**LEA – LEARNING
TECHNOLOGY
ACCELERATOR**

[>WEBSITE<](#)

**OTHER PCP PROJECTS
H2020 FUNDED**

[>WEBSITE<](#)

✓✓ [Guidance on Innovation Procurement](#) (European Commission – DG GROW, 2018), in particular section 4, describes tools and procedures related to public procurement, while listing its several steps and highlighting the tools specifically addressed to innovation procurement by splitting the section into two parts: one dedicated to “Innovation-friendly tools for all types of [procurement] procedures”, and another focused on “Specific innovation friendly procurement procedures”.

✓✓ [EAFIP Toolkit](#), in particular:

- **Module 2:** An operational module addressed to public procurers aimed at clarifying the pre-requisites and key steps to design and implement an innovation procurement process (PCP and PPI); and
- **Module 3:** A legal / operational module addressed to legal services aimed at clarifying legal issues and provide practical ‘how-to’ guidelines, supported by templates.

✚ [EIPonAHA - 3.2.2 - INSPIRE Project: PCP/ PPI Toolkit](#) (INSPIRE Project, 2015). This guide introduces the reader to the PCP/PPI procedures, presenting its main steps and some of the relevant aspects when procuring innovation and the kind of problems that a careful procurement design and management could solve. To explain “how” to approach the main steps of the end-to-end procurement process, this guide provides real-life examples.

✚ LEA materials, specifically those listed on “Support for Procurers” section: <https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/procurers/>

✚ Other PCP Projects H2020 funded:

- A list can be found in the following link: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/eu-funded-projects>
- The brochure entitled [“Innovation Procurement - The power of the public purse”](#) (2019) also offers the list and a summary of the EU funded procurement projects;

A especial note should be given to IMAILE (2014-2018), a PCP project specifically focused on education sector, in particular on personal learning environments (PLE): <http://www.imaile.eu/>. In its website, the user can find [all the materials](#) produced within this project, including:

- ITT documentation;
- and a useful document summarizing the PCP procedure carried out within this project and providing insightful recommendations along all its steps: “Streamlined Learning technology PCP” (2018).

✚ The website www.innovation-procurement.org aggregates all the things related to PPI and PCP. It contains the latest news and events, the European legal framework, policy support and updates on PPI and PCP related projects. Its Resource Centre provides, however, contents mainly related to PPI.

✚ Procurement Forum www.procurement-forum.eu, where procurers and related stakeholders can find a space to discuss, share and connect, as well as to post comments and upload documents, images or videos. Users can create groups, which can be used for discussion or developing and coordinating projects.

BEFORE DRAFTING ITT: GENERAL TIPS

Before drafting the tender documents, EAFIP⁴ recommends discussing and deciding on the following aspects:

- A) Type of procedure to be followed;
- B) The subject-matter of the contract and the technical specifications;
- C) The exclusion criteria;
- D) The selection criteria;
- E) The award criteria;
- F) The use of variants;
- G) The use of value engineering;
- H) The criteria to monitor vendor performance.

When preparing the tender documents, EAFIP⁵ recommends:

- Allocate resources in terms of time, budget and personnel with clear responsibilities for each phase
- Prepare the PCP call for tender
 - ✓ Ensure that solely an open-like procedure will be employed
 - ✓ Draft the contract notice
 - ✓ Draft the Request for tenders/ITT
 - ✓ Draft the technical specifications by using performance/functional based specifications
 - ✓ Don't over specify
 - ✓ Draft selection, exclusion, award and assessment (for monitoring/ex-post evaluation) criteria
 - ✓ Draft the template for the framework agreement and Phase contracts
- Make sure to address and ensure:
 - ✓ Phased approach and allocation of resources for each phase
 - ✓ Include specific mention of the intention to select multiple suppliers to enter Phase 1 and subject to evaluations after each phase and call-offs for the next phase continue to Phase 3 with min. 2 suppliers
 - ✓ Explain how the exclusion, selection and award and assessment criteria will be applied in the stepped process of moving from one phase to the other
 - ✓ Address IPR and pricing related issues ensuring that IPR risk/benefit sharing of is done at market price

⁴ EAFIP Toolkit: Module 2, pp. 82, and Module 3, pp. 29

⁵ EAFIP Toolkit: Module 2, pp. 162

✓ Avoid state aid

- Publish the contract notice in TED and actively promote the PCP call for tender EU wide via several promotion channels
- Publish Q&A when the call for tender is open
- Establish an evaluation mechanism / evaluation panel to assess the tenders received
- Ensure competition, non-discrimination, transparency and equal treatment throughout the entire PCP procedure

Although EAFIP recommendations are important, they do not consider any particular sector of activity. Since LEA is focused on the learning technology sector, it is worth referring to IMAILE materials and their tips and recommendations. IMAILE was a PCP H2020 funded Project in the field of Education and Technology — the first one in Europe. In the document entitled “Streamlined Learning technology PCP” (2018, p. 22), IMAILE team recommends:

- Be specific in your “wish-list” of the Challenge Brief including pedagogical, technical and financial benefits.
- Include clause of User rights in the IPR section for future deployment by the procurers.
- Include Open standards as minimum requirements in order to avoid national legislations and requirements for deployment and purchase.
- Include a demo/mockup as output of phase 1.
- Develop a more iterative approach of phase 2 with more interaction/collaboration between the procurers and suppliers. It is also of importance that phase 2 is extended to 8 months in order to have prototypes for testing in real classrooms ready for phase 3.
- Include a clear communication scheme between procurers and suppliers from phase 1-3 to ensure formal dialogue.
- Each PCP phase needs to be broken down into even smaller packages of features and work for agile management and monitoring for suppliers and procurers Ex. Phase 2 packages to demonstrate specific features followed by Phase 3 test phase to test the same features.

PCP INVITATION TO TENDERS / REQUEST FOR TENDERS template

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Terms and conditions - List of acronyms

As used in this document, the following capitalized terms and expressions shall have the meaning ascribed to them below:

“Assessment” / “Evaluation”	means the process of analysis to determine whether the specific requirements relating to a process, system, product, person or body are fulfilled.
“Award Criteria”	means the criteria used to identify the most economically advantageous tender.
“Common Challenge”	means the shared need/problem identified by the procurers, involved in the Buyers Group or in a coordinated procurement, for which a common solution is sought.
“Completion Date”	means the date for the completion of an intermediate phase/milestone/deliverable or for the project as a whole.
“Contractor”	means the awardees, so entity/entities which have been successful in submitting the tender.
“Evaluation committee”	means a committee of experts in the field of the Project, and/or technical experts, and/or general business experts, appointed by the contracting authority(s) in its/their sole discretion.
“End of Phase Report”	means a report in written form to be submitted by the Contractor for that particular Phase, after each completed Phase of the Project, containing all information that is required at the End of Phase Report Form.
“Functional requirements”	means the specifications set out in the Call for Tenders document defining the required characteristics and set of functions and performance levels of the outcome of the Project.
“Intellectual Property Rights”	means any and all patent rights (including but not limited to, extensions, improvement patents, supplementary protection certificates), inventions (whether or not patentable or capable of registration), trademarks, service marks, copyrights, topography rights, design rights and Database rights, (whether or not any of them are registered or registerable and including applications for registration, renewal or extension of any of them), trade secrets and rights of confidence, trade or business names and domain names and including applications for registration, renewal or extension of any of them, and any other rights or forms of protection of a similar nature which have an equivalent or similar effect to any of them which may now or in the future exist anywhere in the world.
“Minimum quality of a report”	means: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the report can be read by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert. - the report gives insight into the tasks performed in, and the results of, the project.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the report is made using the End of Phase Report Form or (if applicable) the milestone report form, and the requirements of this form have been met. <p>the report contains all information and data as required in the relevant Tender Documents.</p>
“Minimum quality of a demonstration”	<p>means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the demonstration can be understood by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert. This could, for instance, be somebody with operational but not technical knowledge; - the demonstration shows how the innovation works, how it can be used and (if applicable) how it is operated and maintained; - the demonstration is accessible to parties appointed by the public procurer unless these are direct competitors of the Contractor (as agreed between the Parties, acting reasonably).
“PCP”	means Pre-Commercial Procurement as defined by the European Commission Communication COM (2007) 799 final, 14.12.2007.
“Pre-existing rights” (i.e., background)	means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any attached rights such as intellectual property rights ('background IPRs') — that is held prior to the signing of the contract.
“Project Intellectual Property Rights”	means new Intellectual Property Rights arising from the Services and/or the Results and excluding Sideground and Pre-existing rights.
“Results” (i.e., foreground)	means any tangible or intangible output, such as data, knowledge or information, that is generated in the contract, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights ('attached IPRs' or 'IPRs attached to the results').
“Satisfactory completion of a Phase”	<p>means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that the work proposed in the submitted tender has been carried out; - that the funds have been allocated and the work has been carried out according to the planned objectives; - that the required reports/demonstrations for that phase have been submitted on time; - that the required reports/demonstrations for that phase are delivered at minimum quality levels; and - that the work has been carried out in compliance with the provisions of the contract.
“Sideground”	means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any attached rights such as intellectual property rights ('sideground IPRs') — that is generated during the timespan of the PCP but not in the PCP and needed to implement the PCP or to exploit the results of the PCP.

<p>“Sub-Contract”</p>	<p>any contract or agreement or proposed contract or agreement between the Contractor and any third party (the "subcontractor") whereby that third party agrees to provide to the Contractor the Services or any part thereof or facilities or services necessary for the provision of the Services or any part thereof or necessary for the management, direction or control of the Services or any part thereof.</p>
<p>“Successful completion”</p>	<p>means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that the contractor has satisfactorily completed all milestones; and - that the results meet the minimum functionality/performance requirements of the challenge description (i.e. the minimum quality/efficiency improvements which the procurers set forward for the innovative solutions to achieve).

1. General context & background

Explain what PCP is and which EU public procurement directive and national public procurement laws apply.

If applicable, detail the funding sources of this PCP and explain that contracts will have additional rules coming from these funding sources.

Mention that this PCP procurement was preceded by an open market consultation (OMC) and provide a link to the summary of the outcomes of this OMC and the Q&A on the project website.

1.1 Introduction to PCP

This procurement is a **pre-commercial procurement (PCP)**.

PCP means that public procurers challenge innovative players on the market, via an open, transparent and competitive process, to develop new solutions for a technologically demanding mid- to long-term challenge that is in the public interest and requires new R&D services.

PCP is characterised by the following **features**:

✘ Competitive development in phases to identify the solutions offering the best value for money

PCP targets situations that require radical innovation or R&D and for which there are typically no solutions on or close to the market yet. Different competing providers may have different ideas for solutions to the problem. As R&D is yet to take place, there is not yet any proof as to which of these potential alternative solutions would best meet customers' needs.

PCP therefore awards R&D contracts to several competing contractors at the same time, in order to compare different approaches to solving the problem. It thus offers innovators an opportunity to show how well their solution compares with others. It also allows a first customer test reference to be obtained from countries of the procurers that will test the solutions.

The R&D is split into **3 phases** (solution design, prototyping, original development and testing of a limited set of 'first' products or services). Evaluations after each phase progressively identify the solutions that offer the best value for money and meet the customers' needs. This phased approach allows successful contractors to improve their offers for the next phase based on lessons learnt and feedback from procurers in the previous phase. Using a phased approach with gradually growing contract sizes per phase also makes it easier for smaller companies to participate in the PCP and enables SMEs to grow their business step-by-step with each phase.

Depending on the outcome of the PCP, procurers may or may not decide to follow-up the PCP with a public procurement to deploy the innovative solutions (PPI).

✘ Public procurement of R&D services

PCP addresses mid- to long-term public procurement needs for which either no commercially stable solutions yet exist on the market, or existing solutions exhibit structural shortcomings that it requires further R&D to resolve. PCP is a way for procurers to trigger the market to develop new solutions that address these shortcomings. PCP focuses on specific identified needs and provides customer feedback to businesses from the early stages of R&D. This improves the likelihood of commercial exploitation of the newly developed solutions.

PCP is explained in the [PCP communication COM/2007/799](#) and the associated [staff working document SEC/2007/1668](#). The R&D services can cover research and development activities ranging from solution exploration and design, to prototyping, right through to the original development of a limited set of 'first' products or services in the form of a test series. Original development of a first product or service may include limited production or supply in order to incorporate the results of field-testing and demonstrate that the product or service is suitable for production or supply in quantity to acceptable quality standards. R&D does not include quantity production or supply to establish the commercial viability or to recover R&D costs.⁶ It also excludes commercial development activities such as incremental adaptations or routine or periodic changes to existing

⁶ See also Article XV(1)(e) [WTO GPA 1994](#) and the Article XIII(1)(f) of the [revised WTO GPA 2014](#).

products, services, production lines, processes or other operations in progress, even if such changes may constitute improvements.

× Open, transparent, non-discriminatory approach — No large-scale deployments

PCP is open to all operators on equal terms, regardless of the size, geographical location or governance structure. There is, however, a place of performance requirement that they must perform a predefined minimum percentage of the contracted R&D services in EU Member States or Horizon 2020 associated countries.

Any subsequent public procurement of innovative solutions (PPI), for the supply of commercial volumes of the solutions, will be carried out under a separate procurement procedure. Providers that did not take part in this PCP (or were not chosen to go through as far as the last phase) will thus still be able to compete on an equal basis in any subsequent procurement looking for contractors to provide a solution on a commercial scale.

Note:

If funded by H2020: please note that the minimum percentage should be set by the procurers so that at least 50% of the contracted R&D services are performed in EU Member States or Horizon 2020 associated countries (please refer to pg.64).

× Sharing of IPR-related risks and benefits under market conditions

PCP procures R&D services at market price, thus providing contractors with a transparent, competitive and reliable source of financing for the early stages of their research and development. Giving each contractor the ownership of the IPRs attached to the results it generates during the PCP means that they can widely exploit the newly developed solutions commercially. In return, the tendered price must contain a financial compensation for keeping the IPR ownership compared to the case where the IPRs would be transferred to the procurers (the tendered price must be the 'non-exclusive development price'). Moreover, the procurers must receive rights to use the R&D results for internal use and licensing rights subject to certain conditions.

① For more information, see *PCP on the [Europa website](#)*.

1.2 Applicable directives and laws

PCP procurements are exempted from the **EU public procurement directives** because the procurers do not retain all the benefits of the R&D (the IPR ownership stays with the contractors).⁷

They are also exempted from the **WTO Government Procurement Agreement (GPA)** because this Agreement does not cover R&D services⁸ (the PCP being limited to such services — and any subsequent PPI procurements relating to commercial-scale supply of such solutions not being part of the PCP procurement).

⁷ See Article 16(f) of Directive [2004/18/EC](#) (Article 14 of Directive [2014/24/EU](#)), Article 24(e) of [Directive 2004/17/EC](#) (Article 32 of Directive [2014/25/EU](#)) and Article 13(f) (j) of Directive [2009/81/EC](#).

⁸ See the EU's Annex IV of Appendix I to the [WTO GPA](#).

PCP procurements do not constitute state aid under the **EU state aid rules**⁹ if they are implemented as defined in the PCP communication¹⁰, namely by following an open, transparent, competitive procedure with risk- and benefit-sharing at market price. (The division of all rights and obligations (*including IPRs*) and the selection and award criteria for all phases must be published at the outset; the PCP must be limited to R&D services and clearly separated from any potential follow-up PPI procurements; PCP contractors may not be given any preferential treatment in a subsequent procurement for provision of the final products or services on a commercial scale.)

ITALY

The law currently regulating public procurement in Italy is the Legislative Decree. n. 50 of 18 April 2016 (Code of Public Contracts).

In addition to the above, the following Italian legal deeds shall also apply to this PPI:

Law of 7 August 1990 n. 241 regarding the general law on administrative proceedings and Presidential Decree of 28 December 2000 n. 445 regarding the consolidated text of the laws and regulations on administrative documentation)

Legislative Decree of 2 July 2010, n. 104 on the reform of administrative judicial procedure),

Legislative Decree of 6 September 2011 n. 159 regarding anti-mafia legislation)

Act of 13 August 2010 n. 136 on the traceability of payments)

Law of 22 April 1941 n. 633 and Legislative Decree of 10 February 2005 n. 30 on the protection of copyright and other rights related to its operation)

Legislative Decree 10 February 2005, n. 30 "Code of industrial property")

Legislative Decree n. 32/2019 "Unblock building sites" converted into Law n.55/2019

Tenderers are required to read, be aware of and comply with all the above-mentioned legislation.

FINLAND

The laws currently regulating public procurement in Finland are the following:

- Act on Public Procurement and Concession Contracts (1397/2016), that provides also the legal basis for PPI implementation (Section 108, p. 2)
- Finnish copyright Act No. 404/1961 of July 8, 1961, as amended up to Act No. 307/2010 of April 30, 2010)
- Market Court Act (99/2013)
- Act on Consideration for the Energy and Environmental Impact of Vehicles in Public Procurement (1509/2011)

⁹ See Point 33 of the [Commission Communication on a framework for state aid for research and development and innovation](#) (C(2014) 3282).

¹⁰ [Commission Communication: Pre-Commercial Procurement: driving innovation to ensure sustainable, high quality public services \(COM\(2007\) 799\)](#) and [PCP staff working document](#) (SEC(2007)1668).

- Act on the Openness of the Government Activities (621/1999)

Tenderers are required to read, be aware of and comply with all the above-mentioned legislation.

PORTUGAL

The laws currently regulating public procurement in Portugal are the following:

- Public Contracts Code (PCC), approved by the [Decree-Law no.18/2008](#) of 29 January, amended by [Law 59/2008](#) of 11 September, [Decree-Law no.223/2009](#) of 11 September, [Decree-Law no.278/2009](#) of 20 October, [Law no.3/2010](#) of 27 April, [Decree-Law no. 131/2010](#) of 14 December, [Law 64-B/2011](#) of 30 December, [Decree-Law no. 149/2012](#) of 12 July, [Decree-Law no.214-G/2015](#) of 2 October, [Decree-Law no. 111-B/2017](#) of 31 August, [Decree-Law no.33/2018](#) of 15 May and, most recently, [Decree-Law no.170/2019](#) of 4 December. The PCC transposes the EU Directives [2014/23/EU](#), of 26 February, [2014/24/EU](#) of 26 February (which repeals Directive 2004/18/EC), [2014/25/EU](#) of 26 February (which repeals Directive 2004/17/EC) and [2014/55/EU](#) of 16 April.

Tenderers are required to read, be aware of and comply with all the above-mentioned legislation.

There are other relevant diplomas, namely:

- the Administrative Procedural Code (approved by [Decree-Law no.4/2015](#) of 7 January) ("APC"), which contains the general rules on administrative procedures;
- the Procedural Code of the Administrative Courts (approved by [Law no.15/2002](#) of 22 February and amended by [Law no.118/2019](#) of 17 September) ("PCAC"), which contains the rules on litigation regarding pre-contractual procedures and public contracts.
- [Decree-Law no.111/2012](#), of 23 May, amended by [Decree-Law no.84/2019](#), of 28 June, which regulates the State's intervention in the definition, conception, preparation, tendering, awarding, modification, supervising and global monitoring of the public-private partnerships and create the Technical Unit for Projects Monitoring.

Sources:

Diário da República Eletrónico: <https://dre.pt/>

"Portugal: Public Procurement 2020": <https://iclg.com/practice-areas/public-procurement-laws-and-regulations/portugal>

SPAIN

The laws currently regulating public procurement in Spain are the following:

- Law 9/2017, of November 8, on Public Sector procurement (LCSP), through which the Directives of the European Parliament and of the Council 2014/23 / EU and 2014/24 / EU are transposed into the Spanish legal system, February 26th, 2014 as well as its deployment regulations.

- Royal Decree Law 3/2020, of 4 February, on urgent measures that include several directives of the European Union in the Spanish legal system in the field of public procurement in certain sectors, of private insurance, of pension plans and funds, of the tax area and of tax litigation.
- Decree Law of the Government of Catalonia, no. 3/2016, of May 31, of urgent measures in the matter of public procurement.
- Royal Decree 1098/2001, of October 12, approving the General Regulations of the Law of Contracts of Public Administrations. (RD1098 / 2001 RGLCAP), in everything not modified or repealed by the aforementioned provisions.

1.3 Funding sources

In case of receiving H2020 funding:

This PCP procurement is part of a project that is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under grant agreement No [insert number] — [insert project acronym] (see [insert project website]).

[OPTION if the procurement also receives funding from other EU programmes (e.g. if there are procurers in the buyers group whose financial contribution to the PCP budget is funded by other EU programmes, for example the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF)]: Moreover, it receives funding from the *[OPTION for EU programmes:* European Union's [insert name of EU programme]] *[OPTION for national programmes co-funded by the EU (e.g. by Regional Funds, Agricultural Funds):* [insert name of national programme] co-financed by the European Union]:

- [insert beneficiary name and grant agreement number and acronym].]

The contracts will therefore be subject to additional rules that come from the EU grant(s).

① For more information, see 'innovation procurement' and 'links to regional policy' in the [Funding & Tenders Portal Online Manual](#).

⚠ Attention: The EU is not participating as a contracting authority in this procurement.

Note:

It is not allowed for one and the same procurer to receive funding for his part of the PCP budget from different EU programmes (e.g. H2020 and ESIF). But it is possible for different procurers in the buyers group to receive funding from different EU sources.

1.4 Open market consultation

The start of this PCP procurement was preceded by an open market consultation (see [summary and Q&A on \[insert project website\]](#)).

LEARN MORE

D3.1. Learntech Accelerator Procurement Analysis (2018). This LEA report provides an overview of the education systems of EU members' states and their legal framework concerning ICT procurement.

URL: https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/resources_publications/

2. Tender profile: Services to be procured, tender closing time, procurers, contracting approach, budget, timetable and IPR

2.1 Description of services to be procured

PCP challenge

Explain the common challenge, and if applicable the sub-challenges, to be addressed and the scope of the R&D services to be procured:

This procurement is for **R&D services** to develop **solutions** to tackle the following **challenge**: [specify briefly the subject and scope of this PCP, e.g. *improving the energy efficiency of buildings*] *[OPTION for PCPs with sub-challenges: and the following sub-challenges: [specify the sub-challenges].]*

This is a common challenge shared by all procurers in the buyers group. *[OPTION for PCPs with sub-challenges: All sub-challenges are shared by all procurers in the buyers group.]*

The **main quality/efficiency improvements** sought for: [indicate the target quality/efficiency and/or functionality/performance improvements, compared to the current best available solutions, e.g. *30 % energy efficiency improvement, interoperability*]

*[OPTION for PCPs that include the purchase of some of the R&D results: The PCP includes the **purchase** of a limited set of [prototype(s)] [and]/[or] [first test products or services] resulting from the R&D.*

Explain clearly who is procuring which/how many prototypes/test products and where and when they need to be delivered.]

Explain the drivers behind the PCP (*i.e. why the solutions are needed: to improve which aspects in the quality and efficiency of the public services that the procurer(s) is/are responsible for; to meet regulatory requirements and/or to meet a need for standardisation or certification*). Explain also why current solutions don't meet the need.

Note:

Ensure that the targets for the quality/efficiency improvements are set so that they clearly enable to make a step-change beyond what currently available solutions can deliver. Use functional or performance-based specifications that include technical minimum requirements that innovative solutions must meet, rather than prescribing a specific solution. Take into account your analysis on the shortcomings of solutions available on the market, the analysis of the needs of the procurers and the outcome of the open market consultation. Alert tenderers, as far as possible, to any specific requirements of the subsequent phases (*e.g. for phase 2: local technical and safety conditions where prototype testing is planned to take place at one of the procurers' labs; for phase 3: local technical, ethics and safety/security requirements for field-testing*). Provide the metrics or indicators that the procurers will use to evaluate and validate, at the end of each PCP

phase, to what extent each competing solution has made progress towards reaching the targets.

For PCPs that include the purchase of a limited set of prototype(s) or first test products or services resulting from the R&D, specify why these are needed for R&D purposes (e.g. if the existing solution used by the procurers has to be destroyed in order to test the new solutions developed during the PCP and/or the procurers need to carry out further testing of the newly developed solutions after the PCP is finished). Specify which and how many prototypes or first products are to be procured.

LEARN MORE

Example PCP challenge description – IMAILE

IMAILE, in its ITT, stated that

IMAILE procurers are looking for the next generation PLE in STEM for Primary and Secondary Education in order to support the challenge of an increased demand of personalized learning in the European classrooms.

The challenge contained five sub-challenges related to pedagogical, technical and societal aspects. In the ITT documentation, IMAILE team provided a detailed description of each of the five sub-challenges, structured around the following points:

- Problem;
- Challenge description;
- Table of specific challenges;
- State of the art;
- Expected impact;
- Minimum functional requirements.

IMAILE finished the challenge description listing all the requirements, while differentiating them by:

- Minimum requirements with high room for innovation;
- Minimum requirements highly important for IMAILE/ PLE commonly addressed;
- Additional requirements with high room for innovation;
- Additional requirements without room for innovation.

Source: IMAILE, [Invitation to Tender: Annex 1 – The Challenge Brief](#), pp. 17

Expected outcomes (per phase)

Describe the objectives, their associated output and results and the tasks to be carried out (milestones and deliverables) for each of the 3 phases (solution design, prototyping, original development and testing of a limited set of 'first' products or services):

EXPECTED OUTCOMES	
PHASE 1: SOLUTION DESIGN	
Objective:	Perform research to: 1. elaborate the solution design and determine the approach to be taken to develop the new solutions and

	2. demonstrate the technical, financial and commercial feasibility of the proposed concepts and approach to meet the procurement need			
Output and results:				
Milestones and deliverables	By when?	How?	Output and results	
Milestones:	M1.1) [milestone 1.1]	[dd.mm.yyyy]	[e.g. sent by email to lead procurer, on-site visit]	...
	M1.2) [milestone 1.2]
			
Deliverables:	D1.1) [deliverable 1.1]			
	D1.1a) [interim deliverable 1.1a]			
	D1.1b) [interim deliverable 1.1b]			
	D1.2) [deliverable 1.2]			
	D1.3) [deliverable 1.3]			
	D1.3a) [interim deliverable 1.3a]			
	D1.4) [deliverable 1.4]			
	...			
PHASE 2: PROTOTYPING				
Objective:	Develop, demonstrate and validate prototypes in lab conditions			
Output and results:				
Milestones and deliverables	By when?	How?	Output and results	
Milestones:	M2.1) [milestone 2.1]	[dd.mm.yyyy]	[e.g. sent by email to lead procurer, on-site visit]	...
	M2.2) [milestone 2.2]	
			
Deliverables:	D2.1) [deliverable 2.1]			
	D2.1a) [interim deliverable 2.1a]			
	D2.1b) [interim deliverable 2.1b]			
	D2.2) [deliverable 2.2]			
	D2.3) [deliverable 2.3]			
	D2.3a) [interim deliverable 2.3a]			
	D2.4) [deliverable 2.4]			
	...			
Points to be addressed in report:				
PHASE 3: DEVELOPMENT & TESTING				
Objective:	Original development and field-testing of a limited set of first [products] [services] (the test series)			
Output and results:				
Milestones and deliverables	By when?	How?	Output and results	
Milestones:	M3.1) [milestone 3.1]	[dd.mm.yyyy]	[e.g. sent by email to lead procurer, on-site visit]	
	M3.2) [milestone 3.2]	...		
			

Deliverables:	D3.1) [deliverable 3.1]			
	D3.1a) [interim deliverable 3.1a]			
	D3.1b) [interim deliverable 3.1b]			
	D3.2) [deliverable 3.2]			
	D3.3) [deliverable 3.3]			
	D3.3a) [interim deliverable 3.3a]			
	D3.4) [deliverable 3.4]			
	...			
Points to be addressed in report:				

Specify the tasks and expected outcomes of each milestone and deliverable in more detail:

M1.1)

M1.2) ...

D1.1)

D1.2) ...

Note:

Do not forget to include the following deliverables:

- for each end-of phase deliverable, a section that explains the IPR measures taken by the contractor to protect the results and lists the names and location of personnel that carried out the R&D activities
- at the start of phase 1, phase 1 project abstracts (in the format required by the EU for publication)
- at the end of phase 1, a summary of the main results achieved by each contractor and conclusions from phase 1 (in the format required by the EU for publication)
- at the start of phase 2, phase 2 project abstracts (in the format required by the EU for publication)
- at the end of phase 2, a summary of the main results achieved by each contractor and conclusions from phase 2 (in the format required by the EU for publication)
- at the end of phase 2, a demonstration to the EU of the prototypes developed during phase 2
- at the start of phase 3, phase 3 project abstracts (in the format required by the EU for publication)
- at the end of phase 3, a summary of the main results achieved by each contractor and conclusions from the PCP in the format required by the EU for publication)
- a deadline by which the contractors must agree on the text for the summary of overall lessons learnt and results achieved from the PCP, for publication
- at the end of phase 3, a final demonstration to the EU of the final products or services developed during the 3 phases.

For phase 2, specify whether prototype validation is expected to be done at the premises of the procurer(s) or the contractor. For PCPs with lots, clarify if there is a need for validating prototypes of contractors from different lots together (to test dependencies between lots and to ensure that building blocks developed in different lots will ultimately work together as expected).

For phase 3, provide information on the timing and the site(s) where the procurers will carry out the testing and validation of the test series. State clearly how many solutions each contractor is expected to develop for the limited test series. Specify whether contractors need to set aside resources for testing the solutions on the premises of *all* or only *some* procurers. Indicate whether they need to plan to have resources available to carry out testing sequentially or in parallel at the different sites. For PCPs with lots, clarify if there is a need for field testing of products/services developed by contractors in different lots together (to test dependencies between lots and to ensure that building blocks developed in different lots ultimately work together as expected).

LEARN MORE

Example PCP expected outcomes – SHUTTLE

SHUTTLE project (2018-2022, focused on forensic investigation) adopted the above structure for the “outcomes expected”. By checking its ITT, we can, thus, have an example of how this section can be filled.

URL: <https://www.shuttle-pcp.eu/shuttle-td-1-call-for-tenders/>

2.2 Tender closing time

Tender closing time will be: [date and hour, e.g. 5 September 2020, 17h00 Brussels time]

2.3 Procurer(s) [and other parties involved in the PCP]

Explain the procurer set-up: which procurer(s) is(are) launching this PCP ITT; if this ITT relates to a single joint procedure or one of several coordinated PCP processes; which are the responsibilities of each involved entity; etc. The following text provides an example of how to present the entities involved in a joint PCP:

This procurement relates to a joint PCP that will be carried out by the following **lead procurer**: [name and country of the lead procurer]

The lead procurer is appointed to coordinate and lead the joint PCP, and to sign and award the framework agreement and the specific contracts for all phases of the PCP, in the name and on behalf of the following **buyers group**:

- [name and country of the member 1 of the buyers group]
- [name and country of the member 2 of the buyers group]
- ...

The lead procurer is [not] part of the buyers group.

The procurers in the buyers group have the following background/profile/responsibilities for:

- [name 1]: [insert responsibilities]
- [name 2]: [insert responsibilities]
-

Explain the responsibilities the procurers in the buyers group have in their respective countries with regards to setting the acquisition and/or regulatory strategy for the innovative solutions. *(For example, a regional health procurer should explain here for how many hospitals in his region it is responsible to procure solutions, how many patients are served by these hospitals, how many of these patients are affected by the problem that the PCP aspires to solve etc. A regional ministry of health should explain for how many citizens (e.g. specific types of patients) it is defining regulations that affect the deployment of solutions in the healthcare sector in its region.)*

[For PCPs with third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP, add: The following entities are not in the buyers group but participate as **third parties giving in-kind contributions** to the procurers for the purpose of carrying out the PCP:

- [name, country]
- [name, country]
- ...

Provide a short description of the responsibilities of the third parties, the type of resources they will put at the disposal of the PCP, and the rights and obligations that the third parties will assume with respect to the PCP, e.g. *the type of information they will have access to, and whether they will participate in certain parts of the PCP implementation such as testing.* Explain that they will not have rights to results or IPRs.]

[For PCPs with preferred partners, add: The following entities are participating as **preferred partners** with an interest in the PCP, but without being part of the buyers group or giving in-kind contributions for carrying out the PCP:

- [name, country]
- [name, country]
- [name, country]

Explain briefly how the preferred partners will be kept informed about the PCP, what type of information concerning the PCP they will have access to and whether they will attend certain parts of the PCP implementation such as product demonstrations and testing. Explain that they will not have rights to results or IPRs.]

Note:

Definitions for the aforementioned roles:

Lead procurer — Appointed by the buyers group to organise and lead the joint procurement; also part of the buyers group, if he contributes to the procurement budget.

Buyers group — The group of procurers that contribute to the procurement budget.

In case of EU funded PCPs: For procurers that participate in the EU grant as sole participants *(i.e. entities representing several members, e.g. a central purchasing body, a European research infrastructure consortium or a European regional*

cooperation group), indicate which of the members contribute to the PCP procurement budget.

Third parties that provide in-kind contributions to the PCP — Entities that are neither lead procurer nor part of the buyers group, but that give in-kind contributions to the PCP.

Preferred partners — Entities that are neither lead procurer nor part of the buyers group nor third parties providing in-kind contributions, but that have a special interest in closely following the PCP (*other potential buyers for the solutions that have expressed a special interest in the PCP; in case of EU funded PCPs: entities involved in the H2020 grant 'related additional networking activities'*).

2.4 Contracting approach

Explain the contracting approach:

The PCP will be implemented by means of a **framework agreement** with call-offs for **specific contracts** for each of the 3 R&D phases (altogether 'contracts').

Following the tendering stage, a framework agreement and a specific contract for phase 1 will be awarded to a minimum of [indicate number: minimum 3] contractors.

A call-off will be organised for phase 2, with the aim of awarding a minimum of [indicate number] phase 2 contracts. Only offers from contractors that successfully completed phase 1 will be eligible for phase 2. The procurers will validate the phase 2 prototypes [identify the site: in the procurer's labs or the contractors' lab].

A second call-off will be organised for phase 3, with the aim of awarding a minimum of [indicate number: minimum 2] phase 3 contracts. Only offers from contractors that successfully completed phase 2 will be eligible for phase 3. Phase 3 field-testing is expected to take place [insert where (e.g. at all the sites where procurers of the buyers group are based)].

The framework agreement will set all the framework conditions for the entire duration of the PCP (covering all the phases). There will be no renegotiation. The framework agreement will remain binding for the duration of all phases for which contractors remain in the PCP. Tenderers that are awarded a framework agreement will also be awarded a specific contract for phase 1 (evaluation of tenders for the framework agreement and phase 1 are combined). Tenderers are therefore asked not only to submit their detailed offer for phase 1, but also to state their goals, and to outline their plans (*including price conditions*) for phases 2 and 3 — thus giving specific details of the steps that would lead to commercial exploitation of the R&D results.

Provide a brief overview of the overall timing of the PCP (*including the expected start and finish dates*) and of the individual phases.

Indicate clearly (in this section and in the time schedule table below) if:

- the offers for the next phase will be requested together with the end-of phase deliverables for the previous phase (in this case all contractors of the previous phase will be invited to make offers for the next phase, successful completion of the previous phase is evaluated before evaluating the offers for the next phase, to determine which offers are eligible to proceed to the evaluation of offers for the next phase)

or if

- the offers for the next phase will be requested only *after* the end-of phase deliverables of the previous phase and after the contractors have been informed of successful completion of the previous phase (in this case only the contractors that successfully completed the previous phase will be invited to make offers for the next phase.)

2.5 Total budget and budget distribution (per phase)

Explain the budgetary set-up, specifying in particular:

- the total budget for the PCP
- the maximum budget per phase (and per lot, where applicable)
- the maximum budget per tender per phase (and per lot, where applicable)
- the 'minimum' number of contractors that are expected to be selected per phase (and per lot, where applicable)
- the maximum duration per phase.

Provide for the flexibility to transfer leftover budget from one phase to the next phase in case you receive offers with lower price than expected: For phases 1 and 2, contracts will be financed until the remaining budget is insufficient to fund the next best tender. The exact number of contracts finally awarded will thus depend on the prices offered and the number of tenders passing the evaluation. As leftover budget from the previous phase will be transferred to the next phase, the total budget available for phases 2 and 3 may eventually be higher than stated here (but the maximum budget per contractor for phases 2 and 3 will remain the same). The lower the average price of tenders, the more contracts can be awarded. However, the total value of the contracts awarded can also be lower than initially expected if there are fewer tenders than expected that meet the minimum evaluation criteria.

Note:

State the minimum instead of the maximum expected number of contractors, to allow more contracts than initially expected to be awarded if there are more high-quality tenders at cheaper prices than expected.

Ensure that the budget distribution of the PCP:

- starts with minimum of 3 contractors and ends with a minimum of 2 contractors in the last phase
- contains a minimum of 3 phases that between them cover the entire PCP lifecycle: solution exploration; prototyping; initial development and testing of a limited set of first products or services. (If needed, each phase may be split up into more phases, e.g. *in complex PCPs.*)

LEARN MORE

Example budget description – IMAILE

IMAILE, in its ITT, after briefly described the procedures which selected suppliers would have to comply with, presented the following budget:

The global available budget for the PCP process is of 3.800.000€ (the available budget for the PCP process does not include VAT) divided as follows for each of the 3 PCP phases:

PCP Phase 1 (10%) Solution Design Exploration	PCP Phase 2 (40%) Prototype Development	PCP Phase 3 (50%) Proof of Concept
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up to 380.000€ available Maximum number of tenders to be awarded: 8 (eight) Maximum price acceptable to be paid by the Contracting Authority to a single project/tender: 47.500€ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up to 1.520.000€ available Maximum number of tenders to be awarded: 4 (four) Maximum price acceptable to be paid by the Contracting Authority to a single project/tender: 380.000€ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up to 1.900.000€ available Maximum number of tenders to be awarded: 2 (two) Maximum price acceptable to be paid by the Contracting Authority to a single project/tender: 950.000€

The global available budget for this call will not be changed and in any case will not be increased.

However, in phases 2 and 3 the available budget for each phase might be higher in case of non-spent budget from the previous phase(s). HALMSTADS KOMMUN [the lead procurer in IMAILE] reserves the right to add the remaining budget (non-spent amount) of phase 1 into the pot of the phase 2 or 3 or to add remaining budget (non-spent amount) of phase 2 into the pot of the phase 3.

In each of the PCP phases and for each of the awarded projects, payment schedule will be as follows:

PCP Phase 1 (10%) Solution Design Exploration	PCP Phase 2 (40%) Prototype Development	PCP Phase 3 (50%) Proof of Concept
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advance payment of 40% of the project budget upon signature of the framework contract starting phase 1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advance payment of 40% of the project budget upon signature of the contract starting phase 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advance payment of 40% of the project budget upon signature of the contract starting phase 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final payment after analysis of the end of phase 1 report and costs incurred up to the total project budget approved (maximum of 60% of the project budget) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final payment after analysis of the end of phase 2 report and costs incurred up to the total project budget approved (maximum of 60% of the project budget) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final payment after analysis of the end of phase 3 report and costs incurred up to the total project budget approved (maximum of 60% of the project budget)

Source: IMAILE, [Invitation to Tender](#), pp. 8

LEA EXPLORATION

Example budget

Within LEA, procurers interested in launching a PCP in the near future, with the support of the other partners, have already explored a possible budget to their PCP. The exercise is presented below:

	Duration	Budget*	# Expected R&D providers	Max. individual budget*
Development of innovative concept	approx. 4+1 months	840K€	8-10	84K€
Prototyping	approx. 8+1 months	1680K€	4-5	336K€
Original development of a limited volume of first solutions in the form of test series and field testing	approx. 12 months	1680K€	3-4	420K€
		4200K€		840K€

*including applicable VAT rate

2.6 Time schedule

Explain the planned time schedule:

Planned time schedule	
Date	Activity
	First tender procedure (framework agreement and phase 1 contracts)
[dd.mm.yyyy]	Publication of contract notice in TED
...	Deadline for requesting tender documents
	Deadline for submitting questions about tender documents
	Deadline for lead procurer to publish replies to questions (Q&A document)
	Deadline for submission of tenders for the framework agreement and phase 1
	Opening of tenders
	Tenderers notified of decision on awarding contracts
	Standstill period
	Signing of framework agreements and phase 1 specific contracts
	Publication of contract award notice in TED
	<u>Implementation of phase 1</u>
	Start of phase 1
	Names of winning phase 1 contractors and their project abstracts to be sent to EU (template) and published on [insert acronym] PCP project website
	Visit of phase 1 contractors to the premises(s) of the procurer(s) to learn about the operational boundary conditions governing the design of targeted solutions
	Deadline for phase 1 interim milestone(s)/interim deliverable(s)
	Visit(s) of the phase 1 supervisor/monitoring team to the contractor's premises to check completion of milestone(s)/interim deliverable(s)

	Feedback from phase 1 supervisor/monitoring team on phase 1 interim milestone(s)/interim deliverable(s)
	Interim payments (if applicable)
	Deadline for phase 1 final milestone(s)/final report/deliverable(s)
	Assessment of phase 1 final milestone(s)/final report/deliverable(s)
	Phase 1 contractors notified as to whether they have completed this phase satisfactorily and successfully
	End of phase 1
	Summary of the results and conclusions achieved by each contractor during the phase sent to EU (template)
	Payment of balance for phase 1 to contractors that completed this phase satisfactorily
	<u>Second tender procedure (call-off for phase 2)</u>
	Launch call-off for phase 2 (only offers from contractors that successfully completed phase 1 are eligible)
	Deadline for submitting questions on phase 2 call-off documents
	Deadline for lead procurer to circulate replies to questions to phase 2 tenderers
	Deadline for submitting phase 2 offers
	Opening of phase 2 offers
	Contractors notified of decision on awarding phase 2 contracts
	Signing of phase 2 specific contracts
	<u>Implementation phase 2</u>
	Start of phase 2
	Names of winning phase 2 contractors and their project abstracts to be sent to EU (template) and published on [insert acronym] PCP project website
	Visit of phase 2 contractors to the premises(s) of the procurer(s), where applicable
	Deadline for phase 2 interim milestone(s)/deliverable(s)
	Visit(s) of the phase 2 supervisor/monitoring team to the contractor's premises to check completion of interim milestone(s)/deliverable(s)
	Feedback from phase 2 supervisor/monitoring team on phase 2 interim milestone(s)/deliverable(s)
	Interim payments (if applicable)
	Lab testing of the prototype developed during phase 2
	Feedback from phase 2 supervisor/monitoring team on lab testing of the prototype
	Deadline for submission of phase 2 final milestone(s)/final report /deliverable(s)
	Demonstration of prototype for the EU technical review of phase 2
	Assessment of phase 2 final milestone(s)/final report/deliverable(s)
	Phase 2 contractors notified as to whether they have completed this phase satisfactorily and successfully

	End of phase 2
	Summary of the results and conclusions achieved by each contractor during the phase sent to EU (template)
	Payment of balance for phase 2 to contractors that completed this phase satisfactorily
	<u>Third tender procedure (call-off for phase 3)</u>
	Launch call-off for phase 3 (only offers from contractors that successfully completed phase 2 are eligible)
	Deadline for submitting questions about phase 3 call-off documents
	Deadline for lead procurer to circulate replies to questions to phase 3 tenderers
	Deadline for submitting phase 3 offers
	Opening of phase 3 offers
	Contractors notified of decision to award phase 3 contracts
	Signing of phase 3 specific contracts
	<u>Implementation phase 3</u>
	Start of phase 3
	Names of winning phase 3 contractors and their project abstracts to be sent to EU (template) and published on [insert acronym] PCP project website
	Visit of phase 3 contractors to premises(s) of procurer(s), where applicable
	Deadline for phase 3 interim milestone(s)/deliverable(s)
	Visit(s) of the phase 3 /monitoring team to the contractor's premises to check completion of phase 3 interim milestone(s)/deliverable(s)
	Feedback from phase 3 monitoring supervisor/monitoring team on phase 3 interim milestone(s)/deliverable(s)
	Interim payments (if applicable)
	Field-testing of products/services developed during phase 3
	Feedback from phase 3 supervisor/monitoring team on field-testing of the products/services
	Deadline for submission of phase 3 final milestone(s)/final report/ deliverable(s)
	Final demonstration of products/services developed during phase 3 (<i>including to EU representatives</i>)
	Assessment of phase 3 final milestone(s)/final report/deliverable(s)
	Phase 3 contractors notified as to whether they have completed this phase satisfactorily and successfully
	End of phase 3
	Summary of the results and conclusions achieved by each contractor during the PCP sent to EU for publication purposes (template).
	Payment of balance for phase 3 to contractors that completed this phase satisfactorily

Note:**Call for Tender**

When planning the period for submission of tenders, please consider the nature and complexity of the procedure and the time required for preparing and submitting tenders.

If the PCP is funded under H2020, as a general recommendation to enhance innovation, the PCP call for tender must remain open for submission of tenders for at least 60 days.

ITALY

According to the Italian legal framework, in case of open procedure, a minimum time limit of **35 days** shall be set aside for submitting tender. The tendering shall be shortened by 5 days than the minimum time limits imposed in case of procurement made within a dynamic purchasing system.

FINLAND

According to the Finland legal framework, a minimum time limit of **30 days**, reckoned from the date of sending the contract notice, shall be set aside for submitting tenders.

PORTUGAL

In Portugal, if the call for tenders is subject to publication in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU), the minimum time limit for presenting applications is, in general, **30 days**. Partnerships for innovation are subsidiary of Negotiation Procedure (Article 218.º-A of the [Public Contracts Code](#) - PCC), which requires a minimum of 30 days for submitting tenders. This time limit may be reduced, accordingly specific or urgent conditions (Article 198.º of the PCC).

SPAIN

According to the Spanish procurement law, in open procedures for awarding contracts subject to harmonized regulation, the deadline for submitting proposals shall not be less than **35 days**, for works, supplies and services contracts, and **30 days** for works and services concessions, counted from the date of sending the tender notice to the Publications Office of the European Union. Article 156 from the Public Sector Contracts, also foresees some exceptions. For those contracts not subject to harmonized regulation, the deadline for submitting proposals shall not be less than 15 days, counted from the day following the publication of the contract tender notice in the contractor profile. In the contracts of works and concession of works and concession of services, the term will be at least 26 days.

Standstill period

A 'standstill period' is not specifically required by EU procurement rules for PCPs. However, it is recommendable to have a 'standstill period' between the award decision and the signing of the Framework Agreement, since, during this period, interested parties can challenge the result of the evaluation. (EAFIP – Module 3, pp. 80)

ITALY

The Italian stand still discipline, which is configured in the art. 32, co 9 of Legislative Decree 50 of 2016 requires that "the contract cannot be stipulated before **35 days** from the dispatch of the communication of awarding provisions". The term of thirty-five days has been coordinated with the term of judicial appeal of thirty, for the specific purpose of avoiding the stipulation of the contract under pending judgment. The novelty in these provisions is the exclusion of the application of the stand&still period in the case of contracts below the community threshold. In this regard, art. 32, co.10, lett. b) prescribes that "the stand still term referred to in paragraph 9 shall not apply in the of assignments below threshold.

FINLAND

According to the **Finland** procurement legal framework, in a procurement exceeding the European Union threshold value and in a service procurement or concession contract under Schedule E that exceeds the national threshold value, the agreement may be concluded no sooner than **14 days** after the candidate or tenderer has received or is deemed to have received notice of the decision and instructions for appeal (standstill period). The above mentioned standstill period referred shall be **10 days** in procurements based on a dynamic purchasing system and a framework agreement. No standstill period shall apply in a direct procurement. No standstill period need be observed if: 1) the agreement concerns a procurement to be made on the basis of the framework agreement referred to in section 42; 2) the agreement is concluded with the sole tenderer that submitted an acceptable tender, and no other tenderers or candidates remain in the competitive tendering process whose status is affected by the choice of contractual partner; or 3) the agreement concerns a procurement made within a dynamic purchasing system.

PORTUGAL

In Portugal, the standstill period is perceived as the "audiência prévia". It is not clearly defined for the "Partnership for Innovation" type of contract described in the [Public Contracts Code](#) (PCC). However, taking into account the defined periods for other type of contracts, we can state that the Portuguese PCC recommends that after producing the preliminary report (containing the evaluation of the submitted proposals), the jury might provide a period of at least 3-5 days for candidates pronounce about the evaluation made. After this period, the jury must produce another report and, if any change occurred in the candidates ordering, a new standstill period shall be given.

SPAIN

In Spain Article 153. Formalization of contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th): "If the contract is subject to a special appeal in the field of procurement in accordance with article 44, the formalization may not be made before **15 working days** have passed since the notification of the award has been sent to the bidders and candidates. The Autonomous Communities may increase this period, not exceeding one month".

Time Schedule

Within LEA, procurers, with the support of the other partners, have explored a general time schedule for a PCP to be launched in the near future, as presented below:

By planning the resources and time of a PCP there are two components to consider:

- Enable enough time inside the PCP for qualitative R&D.
- The fast development of the learning technology market outside the PCP.

Based on this, the following length will be appropriate for preparing, launching and managing a PCP procedure (the standstill periods are excluded):

1. PCP Solution& design phase (minimum 4 months +1)
2. PCP Prototype phase (minimum 8 months+1)
3. PCP test phase (minimum 12 months)

Phases	Expected time line
Preparation Need analysis, PIN and market consultation, PCP (ITT) documentation Open call on TED Evaluation of first bids Standstill period to prepare contracts	Total 17 months 11 months 4 months 1 month 1 month
PCP and R&D process Phase 1 Development of concept and evaluation of phase report and output Phase 2 Prototypes and evaluation of phase report and output Phase 3 Test	Total 26 months 4 + 1 months 8 + 1 months 12 months
Gather results towards KPIs Evaluation of final innovations, analysis and gather results	Total 2 months
Total PCP project	45 months

2.7 IPR issues

In PCP, the procurer does not reserve all the benefits of the R&D exclusively for himself. Instead, there is 'sharing' of IPR rights that result from the R&D (remember section 1.1 Introduction to PCP).

In this section, explain clearly how IPR will be dealt in this PCP procedure: indicate that the ownership remains with the contractor, and summarise briefly any access and licensing rights on results that the procurer/buyers group wishes to retain.

Ownership of results (foreground)

Each contractor will keep ownership of the IPRs attached to the results they generate during the PCP implementation. The tendered price is expected to take this into account.

The ownership of the IPRs will be subject to the following:

- the buyers group [or, in case of coordinated PCP, procurer] has the right to:
 - access results, on a royalty-free basis, for their own use

- grant (or to require the contractors to grant) non-exclusive licences to third parties to exploit the results under fair and reasonable conditions (without the right to sub-license)
- the buyers group [or, in case of coordinated PCP, procurer] has the right to require the contractors to transfer ownership of the IPRs if the contractors fail to comply with their obligation to commercially exploit the results (see below) or use the results to the detriment of the public interest (including security interests).

ITALY

The Italian public procurement law and the general terms and conditions for government contracts and guidelines on public procurement do not define a default scenario for distribution of IPR rights between procurers and suppliers in Italy nor define how IPR allocation is best dealt with in public procurement contracts. It is left to the individual responsibility of each Italian procurer to specify clearly the IPR allocation for the procurement in its tender documents so that it stimulates innovation and is compliant with applicable IPR/copyright law. Italian copyright law determines that copyrights belong in an inalienable way to the creator (cannot be waived, licensed or assigned to anyone else).

Only the economic rights can be transferred, assigned or licensed by the creator to another person/entity. If the procurer wants to use the copyright created by a (sub)contractor he must require in the tender specifications the transfer, assignment or a license of the economic rights (e.g. usage, licensing, publication, modification, reproduction rights) at equitable payment. Copyright law protects also scientific work, software and database rights.

In the field of IT procurements, however, the national code of practice for IT procurements in administrations (CAD - Codice dell' Amministrazione Digitale) is hindering industrial innovation in the IT sector by interpreting the copyright law more strictly for IT procurements only

FINLAND

The Finnish public procurement law does not address the issue of IPR allocation or transfer but the general terms for the Finnish government's service and product type public procurement contracts ("JYSE2014 services" and "JYSE2014 supplies") define as default scenario that the public procurer obtains only usage rights while all other IPR rights are left with the contractor. This approach was adopted in line with the Finnish copyright act that assigns copyright to the creator and determines that the moral rights can only be waived to a limited extent by the creator when the use of the work in question is limited in nature and extent. If the procurer wants to use the commissioned work he must require in the tender specifications the transfer, assignment or a license of the economic rights (e.g. usage, licensing, publication, modification, reproduction rights) at equitable payment. Copyright protects also scientific work (product designs, product specifications, tests etc.), computer programs and databases. The act foresees that whoever has legally acquired a computer program may make such copies of the program and make such alterations to the program as are necessary for the use of the program for the intended purpose. This shall also apply to the correction of errors.

PORTUGAL

There is no default scenario for the distribution of IPR rights between procurers and suppliers in Portugal. The Portuguese law, general terms and conditions for government contracts and

guidelines on public procurement do not define how the allocation of IPRs is best dealt with in procurement contracts. It is left to the individual responsibility of each Portuguese procurer to specify clearly the IPR allocation for the procurement in its tender documents so that it stimulates innovation and is compliant with applicable IPR/copyright law. Portuguese copyright law determines that the moral rights related to copyrights belong in an inalienable way to the creator. Even in the existence or conclusion of an agreement for a commissioned work (e.g. public procurement) and even if economic rights are transferred, the creator shall continue to enjoy his moral rights. Only the economic rights can be transferred, assigned or licensed by the creator to another person/entity, on condition that there is a written agreement specifying this (e.g. a public procurement contract). In the absence of such written agreement, the Portuguese copyright law assigns by default copyright ownership to the creator. Therefore if the procurer wants to use the work or the copyright owned by the creator he needs to require in the tender specifications the assignment or a license of the economic rights that he needs (e.g. usage, licensing, publication, modification, reproduction rights), according to the article 49º of the Code of Public Contracts (CPC), at equitable payment. Copyright law protects also scientific work, software and database rights.

SPAIN

According to the Spanish Law of Public Sector Contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th) (9/2017) the bid can specify whether the transfer of intellectual or industrial property rights will be required, notwithstanding the provisions of article 308 regarding service contracts. Article 308 of Law of Public Sector Procurement (9/2017) establishes that unless otherwise provided in the administrative clauses or in the contractual document, service contracts that have as their object the development and making available of products protected by an intellectual or industrial property right shall carry coupled with the transfer of this to the contracting Administration. In any case, and even when the transfer of intellectual property rights is excluded, the contracting authority may always authorize the use of the corresponding product to entities, agencies and entities belonging to the public sector

In addition to this, article 10 of the of Royal Legislative Decree 1/1996, of April 12, approving the consolidated text of the Intellectual Property Law, regularizing, clarifying and harmonizing the current legal provisions on the subject, describes the contents considered as Intellectual property.

Commercial exploitation of results

Explain to potentially interested tenderers that there is potential for them to commercially exploit the results of the R&D developed within this PCP. Describe the potential market (and its estimated size) for the results achieved in the PCP.

[The market potential of the results is estimated at [insert available figures for the expected size and type of the potential total market size, i.e. beyond the PCP procurers].]

The contractors are expected to start commercial exploitation of the results at the latest [insert number of years (minimum of four years after the end of the H2020 grant)] years after the end of the framework agreement.

Provide information about:

- whether contractors are required to undertake specific activities beyond product development to commercially exploit the results (e.g. certification of solutions or contribution to standardisation)
- activities that the procurers themselves plan to undertake to help remove barriers to the introduction onto the market of the solutions to be developed during the PCP (e.g. promotion of R&D results among other public procurers, contribution made by the demand side to regulation, standardisation, and certification).

The feasibility of the business plan to commercially exploit the R&D results will be assessed as part of the award criteria.

Declaration of pre-existing rights (background)

Explain that the ownership of pre-existing rights will remain unchanged and that both tenderers and procurers will have to list pre-existing rights.

The ownership of pre-existing rights will remain unchanged.

In order to be able to distinguish clearly between results and pre-existing rights (and to establish which pre-existing rights are held by whom):

- tenderers are requested to list the pre-existing rights for their proposed solution in their offers
- procurers and contractors will be requested to establish a list of pre-existing rights to be used before the start of the contract.

[OPTION if already known that NO relevant background is held by lead procurer, buyers group and third parties providing in-kind contributions: The procurers [and third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP] do not hold any pre-existing rights relevant to the PCP contracts.]

[OPTION if already known that relevant background is held by lead procurer, buyers group or third parties providing in-kind contributions: The following pre-existing rights are already known: [list all pre-existing rights that tenderers should be aware about to prepare their offer — and specify those that are available for use and those that must be used to build upon for carrying out the R&D for the PCP].]

The framework agreement will contain a provision that describes in more detail the rights and obligations of the different parties regarding the pre-existing rights and results.

Note: The background meant here is not the same background as in the H2020 grant agreement (here it relates to the procurement; there it relates to the grant agreement).

3. Evaluation of tenders

3.1 Eligible tenderers, joint tenders and subcontracting

Explain that the call for tenders is open to all operators (companies or other type of legal entities):

Participation in the tendering procedure is **open** on equal terms to **all types of operators from any country**, regardless of their geographic location, size or governance structure.

Tenders may be submitted by a **single entity** or in collaboration with others. The latter can involve either submitting a **joint tender** or subcontracting, or a combination of the two approaches.

For joint tenders:

- explain that the group of tenderers must assume joint and several liability for the performance of the contract
- require that the group of tenderers must mandate one of them with the power to sign the framework agreement and specific contracts provide in their name and on their behalf ('lead contractor')

For subcontracting:

- specify if there are restrictions on the allowed amount(s) that can be subcontracted
- indicate the provisions of national law that apply to subcontracting
- explain that the tender must mention which parts of the contract will be subcontracted
- specify that the contractors remain fully liable to the procurers for the performance of the contract (if applicable, subcontracts must reflect the rules of the H2020 grant agreement, *including as relates to the place of performance, the definition of R&D services, confidentiality, results and IPRs, the visibility of EU funding, conflicts of interest, language, obligation to provide information and keep records, audits and checks by the EU, the processing of personal data, liability for damages and ethics and security requirements*).

Participation in the **open market consultation** is not a condition for submitting a tender.

⚠ Attention:

If applicable: There will, however, be a requirement relating to the place of performance of the R&D services (*see below*).

For phases 2 and 3, participation is limited to tenderers that successfully completed the preceding phase.

Note: "In PCPs, procurers have the possibility to request tenderers to perform a part of the R&D that is relevant for the object of the contract in the territory defined by the EU Member States and the countries that have a Stabilization or Association agreement with the EU in the context of the EU neighbourhood policy." (EAFIP – Module 2, pp. 96)

ITALY

The law currently regulating public procurement in **Italy** foreseen the following obligations and rules, which are provided for a need for completeness.

Availment

According to art. 89, D.Lgs. 50/2016, with regard to criteria relating to economic and financial standing and to criteria relating to technical and professional ability tenderers,

may, where appropriate and for a particular contract, rely on the capacities of other entities, regardless of the legal nature of the links which it has with them.

About criteria relating to the educational and professional qualifications or to the relevant professional experience, economic operators may however only rely on the capacities of other entities where the latter will perform the works or services for which these capacities are required. Where tenderers want to rely on the capacities of other entities, it shall prove to the contracting authority that it will have at its disposal the resources necessary, for example, by producing a commitment by those entities to that effect.

Specific rules for participation and causes of exclusion

It is forbidden for bidders to take part to the tender as member of more than one temporary business grouping or ordinary consortium or aggregations of companies belonging to a business network (hereinafter aggregation of network companies).

It is forbidden for bidders that participate in this tender procedure in partnership with other bidders or as members of ordinary consortia, to also participate individually.

It is forbidden for bidders that participate in this tender procedure as members of aggregation of network companies to also participate individually.

Companies belonging to the partnership not participating to the tender may submit an offer, for the same tender, as single entities or in a joint bid.

When submitting a bid in response to this Call for Tender, a consortium must specify on behalf of which companies belonging to the consortium the latter is bidding; therefore, these companies cannot participate to this tender procedure in any other manner. Failure to comply with this obligation will result in the exclusion from the procedure of both the consortium and the company belonging to the consortium.

In case of a tender submitted by a consortium, the companies belonging to the consortium and appointed for executing the agreement are not allowed to appoint another entity for accomplishing the task.

All members of the Joint tenderers/Temporary Association of Companies/Consortia must accept joint and several liabilities by completing a statement of joint and several liabilities.

For subcontracting:

According to art. 105 D.Lgs.50/2016, subcontracting refers to any contract or agreement between the tenderer and any third party whereby that third party agrees to provide services to the tenderer to enable or assist the tenderer to provide the services or any part thereof to the procurers, to comply with the rights and obligations under the Contract.

The following rules apply:

- The subjects entrusted with the contracts may subcontract the supplies included in the contract, subject to authorization by the contracting authority provided that:

- the subcontractor has not participated in the procedure for awarding the contract;
- the subcontractor is qualified in the relevant category;
- at the time of the offer, the services or parts of services (and supplies, if any) to be subcontracted have been indicated;
- the tenderers demonstrate the absence of the reasons for exclusion referred to in Article 80 by the subcontractors;

Following the Italian legislation, the subcontracting does not exceed 40% (according to the L. n. 55/2019¹³) of the amount of the contract.

The contractors must present the subcontract(s), if any, to the contracting entity at least twenty days before the starting of the execution of the relative services. Upon submission of the subcontracting contract, the contractor also transmits the documentation certifying the subcontractor's possession of the qualification requirements prescribed and the declaration of the subcontractor certifying the absence of the reasons for exclusion referred to in Article 80.

The contractor must replace the subcontractors for whom specific verification has demonstrated the existence of the reasons for exclusion referred to in Article 80.

The (main) contractor is solely responsible towards the contracting authority. The successful tenderer is jointly and severally liable with the subcontractor in relation to the salary payments and contribution obligations, pursuant to article 29 of the legislative decree 10 September 2003, n. 276.

The contractors are required to fully observe the economic and regulatory treatment established by the national and territorial collective work agreements in force for the sector and for the area in which the services are performed. It is also responsible for the subcontractors' compliance with the aforementioned rules with respect to their employees for the services provided under subcontracting.

The contracting authority corresponds payments directly to the subcontractor(s), the amount due for the services they perform in the following cases:

- a) when the subcontractor is a micro-enterprise or small enterprise;
- b) in the event of default by the contractor;
- c) at the request of the subcontractor and if the nature of the contract allows it.

For the services entrusted in subcontracting, the contractor must apply the same unit prices resulting from the awarding, with a drop of no more than twenty percent, in compliance with the quality and performance standards provided for in the contract. The contractor pays the costs of safety and labor, relating to the services entrusted in subcontracting, to the subcontracting companies without any reduction.

¹³ With the entry into force of the Decree-Law n. 32 of 18 April 2019, concerning "Urgent provisions for the re-launch of the public contracts sector, for the acceleration of infrastructural interventions, urban regeneration and reconstruction following seismic events" so-called "Unblock building sites" and converted with modifications in Law 55/2019 on June 2019 the rules relating to subcontracting contained in the Article 105 of the Code of public contracts pursuant to Legislative Decree 18 April 2016, n. 50 have been modified, based on Infraction No. 2015/2273 notified by European Commission on 24th January 2019.

The contractor is jointly and severally liable with the subcontractor for the latter's fulfillment of the safety obligations provided for by current legislation.

The contractor who makes use of subcontracting must attach to the authentic copy of the contract the declaration of the existence of any forms of control or connection pursuant to article 2359 of the civil code with the subcontractor. A similar declaration must be made by each of the participating parties in the case of a temporary grouping, company or consortium. The contracting authority will issue the authorization referred to in paragraph 4 within thirty days of the relevant request; this term can be extended only once, if justified reasons exist. After this deadline without having been provided, the authorization is considered granted. For subcontracting of an amount lower than 2 percent of the amount of the services entrusted or less than 100,000 euros, the terms for the issuance of the authorization by the contracting station are reduced by half.

The execution of the services subcontracted cannot be subject to further subcontracting.

FINLAND

According to the Finnish act on Public contracts and concessions (1397/2016) eligibility of tenderer is regulated as follows:

JOINT TENDERS

According to the Finnish act on Public contracts and concessions (1397/2016) joint tendering is regulated as follows:

Section 92 Group participation in competitive tendering and use of resources of other entities

(1) Suppliers may submit tenders or declare their candidacy as a group.

- The contracting entity may not require a group of candidates or tenderers to have any particular legal form in order to submit a tender or a request to participate.
- A certain legal form may nevertheless be required of a group at the time of agreement if this is necessary for the appropriate performance of the procurement agreement.
- The contracting entity may indicate in the contract notice or call for tenders how candidates and tenderers shall, as a group, jointly satisfy the requirements referred to in section 85 concerning economic and financial standing, the requirements referred to in section 86 concerning technical capacity and professional competence, or the special terms and conditions referred to in section 98.
- The additional terms and conditions concerning such groups of candidates and tenderers shall be objectively justified and proportionate.

(2) A candidate or tenderer may use the resources of other entities for implementing a procurement, irrespective of the legal character of the relations between them.

- A group may also use the resources of other entities for implementing a procurement.
- Resources relating to the competence and experience of the staff of other entities may only be used if the said other entities will implement all or part of the public works contracts or services that are the subject of the procurement.
- A candidate or tenderer or a group thereof shall demonstrate satisfaction of requirements concerning economic and financial standing, technical capacity and professional competence, and other requirements to the contracting entity.

(3) The contracting entity shall require a candidate or tenderer to replace any supplier whose capacities it uses if the said supplier is subject to a mandatory ground for exclusion referred to in section 80, or if the supplier fails to satisfy the suitability requirements referred to in section 83.

The contracting entity may require a candidate or tenderer to replace a supplier that is subject to a discretionary ground for exclusion prescribed in section 81.

(4) If a candidate or tenderer relies on the capacities of other entities in order to satisfy requirements relating to economic and financial standing, then the contracting entity may require the candidate or tenderer and the said other entities to be jointly liable for performing the procurement agreement.

SUBCONTRACTING

According to the Finnish act on Public contracts and concessions (1397/2016) subcontracting (**sections 77-78**) regulated as follows:

- In the contract documents, a contracting entity may require tenderers to indicate in their tenders any part of the contract that they intend to subcontract to third parties, and the proposed subcontractors.
- Such notices shall not limit the primary tenderer's liability for implementing the procurement.
- In the case of public works contracts and service procurements to be performed at facilities under the direct regulatory control of the contracting entity, the contracting entity shall require the selected tenderer, by no later than when performance of the procurement agreement commences, to notify the names, contact details and legal representatives of any subcontractors that are involved in the public works, contract or service procurement if these are known at the time in question.
- The selected tenderer shall also notify changes in such subcontractors and in the foregoing details while the procurement agreement remains in force.
- The contracting entity may extend the duty of notification referred to in subsection 2:
 - o to procurement agreements other than those referred to in subsection 2; and
 - o further along the subcontracting chain.
- In public works contract and service procurements and in assembly and installation work pertaining to a good procurement, the contracting entity may require a tenderer or a member of a group to perform certain critical functions in-house.

- A contracting entity may check whether there are grounds for excluding subcontractors pursuant to section 80 or section 81.
- The contracting entity shall require the tenderer to replace a subcontractor that is subject to some mandatory exclusion criterion. If a subcontractor is subject to a discretionary exclusion criterion, then the contracting entity may require replacement of the subcontractor with another subcontractor.

PORTUGAL

The law currently regulating public procurement in **Portugal** imposes the following obligations and rules:

For subcontracting:

- According to article 168° of the CCP, when, for the purposes of meeting the minimum technical capacity requirements, the applicant has recourse to a third party, irrespective of the link established with them, in particular subcontracting, his application is still made up of a declaration by which the latter unconditionally commit themselves, to perform certain services covered by the contract to be concluded.
- Is stated in article 288° that without prejudice to the provisions regarding the assignment of the contractual position and subcontracting, the contracting party is responsible for the exact and timely execution of the contractual services, in compliance with the agreement, and the contractor cannot pass on to third parties the liabilities assumed before the public contractor.

Limits on assignment and subcontracting by the contractor (article 317)

The assignment of the contractual position and subcontracting are always prohibited:

- where the choice of the contracting party has been determined by direct agreement, in cases where only one entity may be invited;
- The entities covered by the causes of disability provided for in article 55;
- where there is strong evidence that the transfer of the contractual position or subcontracting results from acts, agreements, practices or information liable to distort the competition rules.

In the case of subcontracting, the limit referred to in sub-paragraph a) of the previous paragraph is limited to the services that were the subject of the contract that was decisive for the choice of direct adjustment.

Assignment and subcontracting by the contractor (article 318)

The authorization of subcontracting depends on:

- prior presentation of qualification documents relating to the subcontracted potential required of the subcontractor at the stage of the formation of the contract in question;

- the fulfillment by subcontracted potential of minimum technical capacity or financial capacity requirements where the contract expressly subordinates subcontracting to the evaluation of those capacities or of one of them or the fulfillment by the subcontracted potential of the requirements minimum technical capacity in respect of the services to be subcontracted, where the contracting party makes use of the capacity of potential subcontractors for qualification at the stage of contract formation.
- The contract may prohibit the subcontracting of certain contractual or performance benefits whose accumulated value exceeds a percentage of the contractual price.
- The authorization established in the contract does not exempt, at the moment of assignment or subcontracting, the limits and requirements foreseen, respectively, in the previous article and in the previous numbers.

Authorization to subcontract by the contracting party in the implementation phase (319)

In the stage of performance of the contract, subcontracting is permitted provided that it is authorized by the public contractor.

For the purposes of the authorization referred to in the preceding paragraph, the contracting party shall submit a substantiated proposal and be instructed with all the documents proving the verification of the requirements that would be required for the authorization of subcontracting in the contract itself, in accordance with the provisions of article 318.

Refusal of authorization to subcontract (320)

Subject to the limits laid down in Article 317 and where the subcontracted potential is qualified and brings together the technical and financial capacity, as provided for in the preceding Articles, the public contractor may refuse subcontracting to the contract or deny authorization in the where there is a fear that subcontracting would involve an increased risk of non-compliance with the obligations arising from the contract.

Responsibility of the contractor (321)

In cases of subcontracting, the contractor remains fully liable to the public contractor for the exact and timely fulfilment of all contractual obligations.

SPAIN

JOINT TENDERS

Article 69 of Law of Public Sector Contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th)

1. Business unions that are temporarily constituted for that purpose may contract with the public sector, without the need to formalize them in public deed until the award of the contract in their favor has been made.
2. When, in the exercise of their functions, the contracting body appreciates possible indications of collusion between companies that concur grouped in a temporary union, they will require these companies to justify the reasons to attend in a group.

3. The entrepreneurs who attend grouped in temporary unions will be jointly bound and must appoint a representative or sole representative of the union with sufficient powers to exercise the rights and fulfill the obligations arising from the contract until the termination thereof, without prejudice to the existence of joint powers that may be granted for collections and payments of significant amount

For the purposes of the tender, entrepreneurs wishing to attend associated in a temporary union must indicate the names and circumstances of which they constitute it and the participation of each one, as well as that they assume the commitment to formally become a temporary union in case of being contract winners.

4. The duration of temporary business unions will be at least coincident with that of the contract until its termination

7. Entrepreneurs who are interested in forming the unions referred to in this article may register in the Official Registry of Bidders and Classified Companies of the Public Sector, which will specify this circumstance. If they were already registered in the aforementioned Registry, they should only inform the latter, in the manner established by regulation, of their interest in the indicated sense.

8. If during the processing of a tender and before the formalization of the contract there is a modification of the composition of the temporary union of companies, it will be excluded from the procedure. The alteration of the participation of the companies will not be considered as a modification of the composition as long as the same classification is maintained. The temporary union of companies will also be excluded from the contract award procedure when any or some of the companies that integrate it are prohibited from contracting.

The operations of merger, spin-off and contribution or transfer of branch of activity that are subject to any or some companies integrated in a temporary union will not prevent the continuation of this in the award procedure. In the event that the absorbing company, the resulting from the merger, the beneficiary of the spin-off or the acquirer of the branch of activity, are not companies that are part of the temporary union, it will be necessary that they have full capacity to act, are not included in prohibition of contracting and that the solvency, capacity or classification required is maintained.

9. Point 9 of this article describes the rules that the temporary business unions must observe.

SUBCONTRACTING

Articles 215, 216 and 217 of Law of Public Sector Contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th),

The contractor may arrange with third parties the partial realization of the object of the contract, subject to the provisions of the bid specifications, except that in accordance with the provisions of letters d) and e) of section 2 of this article, the provision or part of it must be executed directly by the first.

In no case may the subcontracting limitation imply that there is an effective restriction of competition, notwithstanding the provisions of this Law regarding contracts of a secret or reserved nature, or those whose execution must be accompanied by special security measures in accordance with legal or regulatory provisions or when required by the protection of the essential interests of State security.

2. The organisation of subcontracts shall be subject to compliance with the following requirements:

a) If so provided in the bid specifications, bidders must indicate in the offer the part of the contract they plan to subcontract, indicating their amount, and the name or business profile, of the subcontractors to whom it will be entrusted.

b) In any case, the contractor must communicate in writing the contracting authority, after the award of the contract and, at the latest, when the execution of the contract begins, the intention to enter into subcontracting, indicating the part of the contract object that intends to subcontract as well as the identity, contact information and legal representative or representatives of the subcontractor. It must also be sufficiently justified the aptitude to execute it in accordance to the technical and human elements that it already has, as well as its experience, and proving that it is not incurred in prohibition of contracting in accordance with article 71.

The accreditation of the subcontractor's aptitude may be carried out immediately after the subcontract is executed if it is necessary to attend to an emergency situation or that requires the adoption of urgent measures and thus is sufficiently justified.

d) In contracts of a secret or reserved nature, or those whose execution must be accompanied by special security measures in accordance with legal or regulatory provisions or when required by the protection of the essential interests of State security, subcontracting will require always express authorization of the contracting authority.

e) In accordance with the provisions of section 4 of article 75, contracts of works, services or services of placement or installation in the context of a supply contract, the contracting bodies may establish the specifications that certain critical tasks cannot be subcontracted, these must be executed directly by the main contractor. The determination of the critical tasks must be justified in the contracting file.

4. Subcontractors shall be bound only before the main contractor who will therefore assume full responsibility for the execution of the contract with the Administration, in strict accordance with the specifications of particular administrative clauses or descriptive document, and the terms of the contract; including compliance with the environmental, social or labor obligations referred to in Article 201, as well as the obligation referred to in the last paragraph of Article 202 (1) referring to the submission to national and Union regulations European data protection.

3.2 Exclusion criteria

List the exclusion criteria and the evidence to be provided that will be used for the evaluation of the tender.

The exclusion criteria are as follows:

Exclusion criteria	Evidence
Include conflict of interest and all mandatory (and if applicable, optional) exclusion criteria according to national law.	Specify the required evidence for each criterion.
A) Conflict of Interest	A) a declaration of honour for 'absence of conflict of interest'
B) Exclusion criteria as defined in Directive 2014/24/EU	Filled ESPD (template available for download here: https://ec.europa.eu/tools/espd)
C) Additional Exclusion as defined in National legislation	Declaration of Honour

⚠️ Tenderers that do not comply with these criteria will be excluded.

Explain each exclusion criterion in more detail:

A) Conflict of interest

Tenderers that are subject to a conflict of interest may be excluded. If there is a potential conflict of interest, tenderers must immediately notify the lead procurer in writing.

A conflict of interest covers both personal and professional conflicts.

Personal conflicts are any situation where the impartial and objective evaluation of tenders and/or implementation of the contract is compromised for reasons relating to economic interests, political or national affinity, family, personal life (e.g. family of emotional ties) or any other shared interest.

Professional conflicts are any situation in which the contractor's (previous or ongoing) professional activities affect the impartial and objective evaluation of tenders and/or implementation of the contract.

⚠️ **Attention:** If an actual or potential conflict of interest arises at a later stage (i.e. during the implementation of the contract), the contractor must contact the lead procurer, who is required to notify the EU and to take steps to rectify the situation. The EU may verify the measures taken and require additional information to be provided and/or further measures to be taken.

B) ...

LEARN MORE

What are exclusion criteria?

"Exclusion criteria are requirements that allow the procurer to exclude economic operators from participating to the procurement procedure on account of their past behaviour (e.g. corruption, money laundering etc.).

The EU public procurement directives set out a list of grounds for exclusion of economic operators from participating to the procurement procedure, which can be used for both PCP47 and PPI. For PPI, several exclusion grounds are mandatory by EU law for public procurers (e.g. participation in criminal organizations, fraud and money laundering etc.)⁴⁸ while others are optional by EU law, but sometimes mandatory by national law (e.g.

bankruptcy, violations of environmental criteria or social obligations, violation of competition rules or of intellectual property rights etc.).

The public procurer is required to ensure the verification of the absence of the reasons of exclusion, when exclusion criteria are used. The exclusion should also be subject to a proportionality check and subject to evidence that the economic operator has taken effective measures to address the exclusion grounds."

Source: EAFIP, Module 2, pp. 94.

ITALY

According to **Italian** legislation, the lead procurer may exclude a bidder in any of the following situations:

- 1) the bidder itself or any person who is a member of its administrative, management or supervisory body or has powers of representation, decision or control therein has been the subject of a conviction by final judgment, by a conviction rendered at the most five years ago or in which an exclusion period set out directly in the conviction continues to be applicable for the following crimes:
 - a) crimes, consummated or attempted, as defined in articles 416, 416-bis of the Italian Penal code or crimes committed by making use of the conditions provided for by the aforementioned art. 416-bis or in order to facilitate the activities of the associations provided for in the same article, as well as for the crimes committed or attempted, as provided for by art. 74 of the Decree of the President of the Republic October 9, 1990, n. 309, from the art. 291 quarter of the decree of the President of the Republic January 23, 1973, n. 43 and from the art. 260 of the legislative decree 3 April 2006, n. 152, as referable to participation in a criminal organization, as defined in art. 2 of the Council Framework Decision 2008/841 / JHA;
 - b) crimes, consummated or attempted, referred to in articles 317, 318, 319, 319-for, 319-quarter, 320, 321, 322, 322-bis, 346-bis, 353, 353-bis, 354, 355 and 356 of the penal code as well as art. 2635 of the civil code;
 - b-bis) false financial statements referred to in articles 2621 and 2622 of the Italian Civil Code;
 - c) fraud, as defined by Article 1 of the Convention on the protection of the European Communities' financial interests;
 - d) terrorist offences or offences linked to terrorist activities, as defined in Articles 1 and 3 of Council Framework Decision of 13 June 2002 on combating terrorism (OJ L 164, 22.6.2002, p. 3). (This exclusion ground also includes inciting or aiding or abetting or attempting to commit an offence, as referred to in Article 4 of that Framework Decision)
 - e) money laundering or terrorist financing and offences referred to in articles 648 bis, 648 ter., 648 ter.1 of Italian Penal Code and terrorist financing as defined in article 1 of Legislative Decree no. 109/2007;
 - f) the exploitation of child labour and other forms of trafficking in human beings defined by Legislative Decree 4 March 2014, n. 24;
 - g) any other offence that determined an incapacity to contract with the public administration as an ancillary punishment.

- 2) the bidder itself or any person who is a member of its administrative, management or supervisory body or has powers of representation, decision or control therein has been the subject of the application of measures referred to in art. 67 of Legislative Decree No. 159/2011 or the existence of an attempt of mafia infiltration as defined in art. 84, paragraph 4 thereof;
- 3) the bidder has breached its obligations relating to the payment of social security, both in the country in which it is established and in Member State of the contracting authority or contracting entity if other than the country of the establishment;
- 4) the bidder has committed serious infringements duly established to the rules on health and safety at work as well as the obligations under Art. 30, paragraph 3 of Legislative Decree 50/2016;
- 5) the bidder is in a state of bankruptcy, compulsory liquidation, of an arrangement with creditors, except in the case of a business continuity agreement, and that no procedure is in progress for the declaration of one of these situations, without prejudice art. 110 of Legislative Decree 50/2016;
- 6) the bidder has been guilty of serious professional misconduct, such as to make his integrity or reliability questionable;
- 7) the bidder has attempted to unduly influence the decision-making process of the contracting authority or obtain confidential information for the purpose of your own benefit or have not provided, even by negligence, false or misleading information likely to influence decisions on exclusion, selection or exclusion the award, or not to have omitted the information due to the correct execution of the selection procedure;
- 8) the bidder has demonstrated significant or persistent deficiencies in the execution of a previous contract or concession contract that caused the termination due to non-compliance or the sentence for damages or other comparable penalties;
- 9) the bidder carries out a distortion of competition deriving from the previous involvement in the preparation of the procurement procedure pursuant to art. 67 of Legislative Decree 50/2016 which can not be resolved by less intrusive measures;
- 10) the bidder has been subject to interdictory sanction referred to in art. 9, paragraph 2, letter c) of the legislative decree 8 June 2001, n. 231 or other sanction that involves the prohibition of contracting with the public administration, including the disqualification provisions set forth in art. 14 of the legislative decree 9 April 2008, n. 81;
- 11) the bidder has presented in the ongoing tender procedure and in the assignments of subcontracts, documentation or untruthful declarations;
- 12) the bidder is mentioned within the ANAC Record for having supplied false information or submitted false documentation in order to get a qualification certificate;
- 13) the bidder has violated the prohibition of fiduciary registration pursuant to art. 17 of the Law of 19 March 1990, n. 55;
- 14) the bidder is not compliant with the rules governing the right to work for the disabled (law 12 March 1999, No. 68);
- 15) the bidder has been a victim of the crimes defined by the articles 317 and 629 of the penal code aggravated pursuant to art. 7 of the Decree-Law of May 13, 1991, n. 152, converted, with modifications, from the law 12 July 1991, n. 203 without reporting

the facts to the judicial authority or recourse the cases provided for by art. 4, first paragraph, of the law November 24th 1981, n. 689;

- 16) the bidder in one of the situations referred to in art. 80, paragraph 1 of Legislative Decree No. 50/2016, limited to the cases in which the final sentence imposed a custodial sentence not exceeding 18 months or recognized the mitigating nature of the collaboration as defined for the individual offences, or in paragraph 5 of the aforementioned art. 80, has not indemnified or committed to compensating any damage caused by the crime or the offence and has adopted the following concrete technical, organizational and personnel-related measures to prevent further crimes or offences.
- 17) the bidder is in relation to another participant in the same procedure of assignment, in a control situation referred to in Article 2359 of the Italian Civil Code or in any report, even de facto, if the control situation or relationship involves that the offers are attributable to a single decision-making centre.

FINLAND

According to the Finnish act on Public contracts and concessions (1397/2016) exclusion criteria are divided into mandatory (section 81) and discretionary (section 82) exclusion criteria

Section 80 Mandatory exclusion criteria

(1) The contracting entity shall issue a decision excluding a candidate or tenderer from competitive tendering if the contracting entity is aware that the candidate or tenderer, a member of its administration or management, or a person exercising representative, managerial or regulatory authority therein has a criminal record indicating a legally final conviction for any of the following offences:

- 1) bribery, as referred to in section 13, aggravated bribery, as referred to in section 14, bribery of a Member of Parliament, as referred to in section 14 a, or aggravated bribery of a Member of Parliament, as referred to in section 14 b of Chapter 16 of the Criminal Code of Finland (39/1889);
- 2) participating in the activity of an organized criminal group, as referred to in section 1 an of Chapter 17 of the Criminal Code of Finland;
- 3) trafficking in human beings, as referred to in section 3, or aggravated trafficking in human beings, as referred to in section 3 an of Chapter 25 of the Criminal Code of Finland;
- 4) tax fraud, as referred to in section 1, aggravated tax fraud, as referred to in section 2, employment pension insurance premium fraud, as referred to in section 4 a, aggravated employment pension insurance premium fraud, as referred to in section 4 b, subsidy fraud, as referred to in section 5, aggravated subsidy fraud, as referred to in section 6, or subsidy misuse, as referred to in section 7 of Chapter 29 of the Criminal Code of Finland;
- 5) giving of bribes in business, as referred to in section 7, aggravated giving of bribes in business, as referred to in section 7 a, acceptance of a bribe in business, as referred to in section 8, or aggravated acceptance of a bribe in business, as referred to in section 8 a of Chapter 30 of the Criminal Code of Finland;
- 6) money laundering, as referred to in section 6, aggravated money laundering, as referred to in section 7, conspiracy for the commission of aggravated money

laundering, as referred to in section 8, or negligent money laundering, as referred to in section 9 of Chapter 32 of the Criminal Code of Finland;

- o 7) offence made with terrorist intent, as referred to in section 1, preparation of an offence to be committed with terrorist intent, as referred to in section 2, directing of a terrorist group, as referred to in section 3, promotion of the activity of a terrorist group, as referred to in section 4, provision of training for the commission of a terrorist offence, as referred to in section 4 a, recruitment for the commission of a terrorist offence, as referred to in section 4 c, or financing of terrorism, as referred to in section 5 of Chapter 34 a of the Criminal Code of Finland.

(2) The contracting entity shall issue a decision excluding a candidate or tenderer from competitive tendering if the contracting entity is aware that a member of the candidate's or tenderer's administration or management, or a person exercising representative, managerial or regulatory authority therein, has a criminal record indicating a legally final conviction for a work safety offence, as referred to in section 1, a working hours offence, as referred to in section 2, work discrimination, as referred to in section 3, extortionate work discrimination, as referred to in section 3 a, violation of the right to organise, as referred to in section 5, or unauthorised use of foreign labour, as referred to in section 6 a of Chapter 47 of the Criminal Code of Finland.

(3) The contracting entity shall also exclude a candidate or tenderer from competitive tendering on the basis of a final conviction for an offence in another state that corresponds to an offence referred to in subsections 1 or 2.

(4) The contracting entity shall also exclude from competitive tendering a candidate or tenderer that has been found by a legally final decision or judgement to have defaulted on a duty to pay the taxes or social security contributions of Finland or of its country of establishment. This provision shall nevertheless not apply if the candidate or tenderer has paid the taxes or social security contributions, or agreed to a binding arrangement for their payment.

(5) A candidate or tenderer shall not be excluded from competitive tendering if more than five years have elapsed since the issuing of a legally final judgement concerning the offence referred to in subsections 1–3, or the default referred to in subsection 4.

Section 81 Discretionary exclusion criteria

(1) The contracting entity may decide to exclude from competitive tendering a candidate or tenderer:

- 1) that is bankrupt or subject to liquidation, that has suspended trading, or whose liabilities have been restructured in a confirmed composition, restructuring programme or other corresponding statutory procedure;
- 2) that is subject to pending bankruptcy, winding up or other proceedings referred to in point 1;
- 3) that the contracting entity can prove has been guilty of grave professional misconduct calling its reliability into question;
- 4) that the contracting entity can prove, otherwise than by legally final decision or judgement, to have defaulted duty to pay the taxes or social security contributions of Finland or of its country of the establishment;
- 5) that has infringed the environmental, social and labour law obligations Finnish or European Union legislation, collective agreements, or the international treaties listed in Annex C, where the contracting entity can prove the infringement;

- 6) that has concluded agreements with other suppliers seeking to distort competition, and the contracting entity can prove that this has occurred;
- 7) whose conflict of interest in the procurement procedure cannot be effectively eliminated by other measures;
- 8) whose participating in preparing the procurement procedure has distorted competition, and the distortion cannot be eliminated by other, less intrusive measures; before the exclusion, the candidate or tenderer shall be given an opportunity to show that its participation in preparing the procurement has not resulted in compromising an impartial and non-discriminatory procurement procedure;
- 9) whose performances in previous procurement agreements or concession contracts have involved significant or repeated shortcomings in implementing some key requirement; it shall be a further condition that the shortcomings led to premature termination, rescission, damages or other corresponding sanctions with respect to the previous agreement in question;
- 10) that has been guilty of material misrepresentation in furnishing the contracting entity with the information referred to in this Chapter, or has failed to supply the required information;
- 11) that has sought to unduly influence the decision-making process of the contracting entity, to obtain confidential information that may confer an undue advantage upon it in the procurement procedure, or to willfully provide misleading information that may have a material influence on decisions concerning the selection of a tenderer or tender.

(2) The provisions of points 3, 5 and 6 of subsection 1 concerning a candidate and tenderer shall also apply when the party guilty of an error or offence or of defaulting on an obligation is a member of the candidate's or tenderer's administration or management, or a person exercising representative, managerial or regulatory authority therein. Discretion concerning an exclusion may also consider such aspects as the gravity of the error, offence or default, the connection to the procurement, the time that has elapsed, and any other consequences incurred.

(3) The provision in point 4 of subsection 1 shall not apply if the candidate or tenderer has paid the taxes or social security contributions, or agreed to a binding arrangement for their payment.

(4) A candidate or tenderer may not be excluded from competitive tendering if more than three years have elapsed since the event referred to in subsection 1.

Portugal

Specific rules for participation and causes of an exclusion applicable in Portugal are the following.

The following entities may not be candidates, competitors or any grouping:

- i) have in any capacity, directly or indirectly, provided advice or technical support in the preparation and preparation of the parts of the procedure which confer on them an advantage which distorts normal conditions of competition;

(j) have endeavoured to unduly influence the decision to hire the competent body, to obtain confidential information likely to confer undue advantage on the procedure, or to have provided erroneous information likely to materially alter exclusion, rating or award decisions;

(k) are covered by conflicts of interest which can not be effectively corrected by other measures less burdensome than exclusion;

(l) have suffered significant or persistent shortcomings in the execution of at least one prior public contract in the last three years, leading to the termination of that contract for non-compliance, to the payment of compensation for non-compliance, to the application of penalties which have the maximum amounts applicable under Article 329 (2) and (3), or equivalent penalties.

See the complete list on article 55° of the CCP

Also, according to article 70° will be excluded from all the proposals that:

a) That they do not present any of the attributes or any of the terms or conditions, under the terms, respectively, of the provisions in paragraphs b) and c) of paragraph 1 of article 57;

(b) which have attributes which infringe the basic parameters laid down in the contract documents or which show any terms or conditions which infringe the performance of the contract to be entered into by the contractor not subject to competition, without prejudice to paragraphs 4 to 6 and (8) to (11);

c) The impossibility of evaluating them by virtue of the form of presentation of some of the respective attributes;

d) That the contractual price would be higher than the base price;

e) An abnormally low price or cost, whose explanations have not been presented or have not been considered in accordance with the provisions of the following article;

f) That the contract to be executed would imply the violation of any applicable legal or regulatory binding;

(g) the existence of strong indications of acts, agreements, practices or information liable to distort competition rules.

The following entities may not be candidates, competitors or any grouping (article 55°):

(a) they are in a state of insolvency, declared by a court judgment, in liquidation, dissolution or cessation of activity, subject to any preventive means of liquidation of assets or in an analogous situation, or have their proceedings pending, except when having a judicial or extrajudicial business recovery plan provided for by law;

b) they have been convicted of a crime that has the force of res judicata for any crime that affects their professional conduct, in the case of natural persons, or, in the case of legal persons, when they have been convicted of such crimes by the legal person or the owners of their organs social management, management or management, and these are ineffective functions, in any case without their rehabilitation having occurred in the meantime;

(c) they have been subject to an administrative penalty for serious misconduct in professional matters, if their rehabilitation has not occurred in the case of natural persons or, in the case of legal persons, they have been application of that administrative sanction the

holders of the social management bodies, direction or management of the same and these are in effectiveness of functions;

(d) their situation is not regularized in respect of social security contributions in Portugal or, where applicable, in the State of which they are nationals or in which their principal place of business is situated;

(e) their situation is not regularized in respect of taxes due in Portugal or, where applicable, in the State of which they are nationals or in which their principal place of business is situated;

(f) they have been subject to the application of ancillary sanction to prohibit participation in public contracts provided for in special legislation, in particular in the case of anti-competitive labour, competition and equality and non-discrimination schemes, and the penalty provided for in Article 460. , during the period fixed in the conviction;

(g) they have been subject to administrative or judicial sanctions for less than two years for the use of legally liable labour social security contributions not declared in accordance with the rules imposing such an obligation in Portugal or in the State of which they are nationals or in which their principal place of business is situated;

h) they have been convicted of a final judgment for any of the following crimes, if in the meantime they have not been rehabilitated, in the case of natural persons or, in the case of legal persons, have been convicted by the crimes of the legal person and the members of its governing bodies, management or management thereof and these are in effect of functions, if in the meantime has not occurred its rehabilitation

i) have in any capacity, directly or indirectly, provided advice or technical support in the preparation and preparation of the parts of the procedure which confer on them an advantage which distorts normal conditions of competition;

(j) have endeavoured to unduly influence the decision to hire the competent body, to obtain confidential information likely to confer undue advantage on the procedure, or to have provided erroneous information likely to materially alter exclusion, rating or award decisions;

(k) are covered by conflicts of interest which can not be effectively corrected by other measures less burdensome than exclusion;

(l) have suffered significant or persistent shortcomings in the execution of at least one prior public contract in the last three years, leading to the termination of that contract for non-compliance, to the payment of compensation for non-compliance, to the application of penalties which have the maximum amounts applicable under Article 329 (2) and (3), or equivalent penalties.

2 - The jury must propose the exclusion of solutions that:

(a) they have been lodged after the expiry of the time limit laid down for their submission;

b) they have been presented in violation of the provisions of article 210;

c) Do not comply with the provisions of the previous article;

(d) they are manifestly inadequate to meet the needs or requirements identified in the descriptive document.

Specific rules for participation and causes of exclusion

2 - The jury must propose the exclusion of solutions that:

- (a) they have been lodged after the expiry of the time limit laid down for their submission;
- b) they have been presented in violation of the provisions of article 210;
- c) Do not comply with the provisions of the previous article;
- (d) they are manifestly inadequate to meet the needs or requirements identified in the descriptive document.

Also, according to article 70° will be excluded from all the proposals that:

- a) That they do not present any of the attributes or any of the terms or conditions, under the terms, respectively, of the provisions in paragraphs b) and c) of paragraph 1 of article 57;
- (b) which have attributes which infringe the basic parameters laid down in the contract documents or which show any terms or conditions which infringe the performance of the contract to be entered into by the contractor not subject to competition, without prejudice to paragraphs 4 to 6 and (8) to (11);
- c) The impossibility of evaluating them by virtue of the form of presentation of some of the respective attributes;
- d) That the contractual price would be higher than the base price;
- e) An abnormally low price or cost, whose explanations have not been presented or have not been considered in accordance with the provisions of the following article;
- f) That the contract to be executed would imply the violation of any applicable legal or regulatory binding;
- (g) the existence of strong indications of acts, agreements, practices or information liable to distort competition rules.

SPAIN

Article 64. Fight against corruption and prevention of conflicts of interest of Law of Public Sector Contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th)

1. The contracting bodies shall take appropriate measures to combat fraud, favoritism and corruption, and prevent, detect and effectively resolve conflicts of interest that may arise in bidding procedures in order to avoid any distortion of competition and guarantee transparency in the procedure and equal treatment to all candidates and bidders.

2. For these purposes, the concept of conflict of interest shall cover, at least, any situation in which the personnel at the service of the contracting authority, who also participate in the development of the tender procedure or may influence the outcome thereof, have directly or indirectly a financial, economic or personal interest that might appear to compromise its impartiality and independence in the context of the tender procedure.

Those persons or entities that have knowledge of a possible conflict of interest should immediately inform the contracting authority.

Section 1st. Suitability to contract with the Public Sector – contain articles 65-70

Article 65. Conditions of suitability.

1. Only natural or legal persons, Spanish or foreign, who have full capacity to act, are not involved in any prohibition to contract, and prove their economic and financial and technical or professional solvency or, when this law requests it, are duly classified.

When, as determined by the applicable regulations, the contractor is required certain requirements related to his organization, destination of his benefits, financing system or others to be able to participate in the corresponding awarding procedure, these must be accredited by the tenderer when attending in the same.

2. The contractors must also have the business or professional qualification that, where appropriate, is required for the realization of the benefits that constitute the object of the contract.

3. In the subsidized contracts referred to in article 23 of this Law, the contractor must prove its solvency and may not be subject to the prohibition of hiring referred to in letter a) of section 1 of article 71.

Section 2nd. Impossibility to contract (articles 71-73)

art.71 of Law of Public Sector Contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th, describes the Impossibility to contract.

1. The persons in whom one of the following circumstances concurs may not contract with the entities provided for in article 3 of this Law with the effects established in article 73:

a) Having been convicted by a final sentence for terrorist offenses, constitution or integration of a criminal organization or group, illegal association, illegal financing of political parties, trafficking of human beings, business corruption, influence peddling, bribery, fraud, crimes against the Public Treasury and Social Security, crimes against workers' rights, prevarication, embezzlement, prohibited negotiations to officials, money laundering, crimes related to land management and urban planning, heritage protection history and the environment, or the penalty of special disqualification for the exercise of profession, trade, industry or trade.

The prohibition of contracting will reach legal persons that are declared criminally responsible, and those whose administrators or representatives, whether in fact or by law, either by their position or representation and until their termination, will be in the situation mentioned in this section.

b) Having been firmly sanctioned for serious infringement in professional matters that calls into question their integrity, market discipline, distortion of competition, labor integration and equal opportunities and non-discrimination of persons with disabilities, or of foreigners, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations; or for a very serious infraction in environmental matters in accordance with what is established in current regulations, or for a very serious infraction in labor or social matters, in accordance with the provisions of the consolidated text of the Law on Infractions and Sanctions in the Social Order, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 5/2000, of August 4, as well as the serious infraction provided for in article 22.2 of the aforementioned text.

c) Have requested the declaration of voluntary insolvency, have been declared insolvent in any procedure, have been declared insolvent, unless an agreement has become effective or an extrajudicial payment agreement file has been initiated, subject to judicial intervention or have been disqualified according to Law 22/2003, of July 9, Bankruptcy, without having concluded the period of disqualification established in the judgment of qualification of the contest.

d) Not being up to date in compliance with the tax or Social Security obligations imposed by the provisions in force, in the terms determined by regulation; or in the case of companies with 50 or more workers, not fulfilling the requirement that at least 2 percent of their employees be workers with disabilities, in accordance with article 42 of Royal Legislative Decree 1/2013, of November 29, which approves the consolidated text of the General Law on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and their social inclusion, under the conditions determined by regulation; or in the case of companies with more than 250 workers, not

complying with the obligation to have an equality plan in accordance with the provisions of article 45 of Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the equality of women and men

e) Having incurred falsehood when making the responsible declaration referred to in article 140 or when providing any other information regarding its capacity and solvency, or having breached, for reasons attributable to it, the obligation to communicate the information provided in Article 82.4 and Article 343.1.

f) To be affected by a prohibition of contracting imposed by virtue of firm administrative sanction, in accordance with the provisions of Law 38/2003, of November 17, General Subsidies, or Law 58/2003, of December 17, General Tax.

The present cause of prohibition of contracting will cease to apply when the contracting authority, in accordance with the provisions of Article 72.1, verifies that the company has fulfilled its payment obligations or entered into a binding agreement with a view to paying the amounts due, including accrued interest or fines imposed.

g) To be, the natural person or the administrators of the legal person, in any of the cases of Law 3/2015, of March 30, regulating the exercise of the high positions of the General State Administration or the respective norms of the Communities Autonomous, of Law 53/1984, of December 26, on Incompatibilities of Personnel in the Service of Public Administrations or dealing with any of the elective positions regulated in Organic Law 5/1985, of June 19, of the General Electoral Regime, in the terms established therein.

The prohibition will reach the legal persons in whose capital the personnel and the high positions referred to in the previous paragraph participate, in the terms and amounts established in the aforementioned legislation, as well as the elected positions at their service.

The prohibition also extends, in both cases, to the spouses, persons linked with an analogous relationship of emotional coexistence, ascendants and descendants, as well as to relatives in the second degree by consanguinity or affinity of the persons referred to in the preceding paragraphs, when there is a conflict of interest with the holder of the contracting authority or the holders of the bodies to which the power to contract or those who substitute the former has been delegated.

2. In addition to those provided in the previous section, the following are circumstances that will prevent employers from contracting with the entities included in article 3 of this Law, under the conditions established in article 73, the following:

a) To have unduly withdrawn its proposal or candidacy in an adjudication procedure, or to have made it impossible to award the contract in its favor for not completing the provisions of section 2 of article 150 within the period indicated by means of fraud, negligence or negligence.

b) Having failed to formalize the contract, which has been awarded in its favor, within the time limits provided in Article 153 for cause attributable to the successful tenderer.

c) Having breached the clauses that are essential in the contract, including the special conditions of execution established in accordance with the provisions of article 202, when said breach had been defined in the specifications or in the contract as a serious infringement, concurring intentionally, fault or negligence in the employer, and provided that it has resulted in the imposition of penalties or compensation for damages.

d) Have resulted, because had been found guilty, into the firm termination of any contract concluded with an entity of those included in Article 3 of this Law. The prohibition will reach companies whose contract has been resolved for the contractor's guilty breach of the obligations that the specifications have qualified as essential in accordance with the provisions of article 211.1.f).

3. The prohibitions on hiring will also affect those companies from which, by reason of the people who govern them or from other circumstances, it can be presumed that they are continuation or that derive, by transformation, merger or succession, from other companies in which would have attended those

h) Have hired people for whom the breach referred to in article 15.1 of Law 3/2015, of March 30, regulating the exercise of high office of the State has been published in the «Official State Gazette» General Administration of the State or in the respective norms of the Autonomous Communities, for having come to provide services in companies or private companies directly related to the competences of the position held during the two years following the date of termination therein. The prohibition of hiring will remain for as long as the person hired with the maximum limit of two years from the termination as senior office remains within the organization of the company.

3.3 Selection criteria

List the selection criteria and the evidence to be provided.

The selection criteria are as follows:

Selection criteria	Evidence
A) Ability to perform R&D up to original development of the first products or services and to commercially exploit the results of the PCP, including intangible results in particular IPRs	<p>Description of the capacity, materials and equipment that are available to the tenderer for research, prototyping and limited production and supply of the first set of products or services</p> <p>Description of the financial and organisational structures that are available to the tenderer for management, exploitation and transfer of IPRs and for generating revenue by marketing commercial applications of the results</p>
B) ...	

⚠ Tenderers that do not comply with these criteria will be excluded.

Explain each selection criterion in more detail:

A) Ability to perform R&D up to original development of the first products or services and to commercially exploit the results of the PCP, including intangible results in particular IPRs

Tenderers must have:

- the capacity, tools, material and equipment to:
 - carry out research and lab prototyping
 - produce and supply a limited set of first products or services and demonstrate that these products or services are suitable for production or supply in quantity and to quality standards defined by the procurers
- the financial and organisational structures to
 - manage, exploit and transfer or sell the results of the PCP (*including tangible and intangible results, such as new product designs and IPRs*)
 - generate revenue by marketing commercial applications of the results (*directly or through subcontractors or licensees*).

B) ...

⚠ Attention: Should there be any doubt as to any of these criteria, tenderers may be requested to provide additional information.

Note:

Avoid selection criteria that are based on disproportionate qualification and financial guarantee requirements (e.g. with regard to references from past customers, references for professional or technical qualifications and minimum turnover). Instead, use the business plan as one of the award criteria for deciding whether to award a contract (i.e. by requiring tenderers to show that they are able, during the PCP, to gradually build up sufficient financial capacity to successfully market their results).

LEARN MORE**What are selection criteria?**

“Selection criteria are requirements related to the suitability of an economic operator to pursue the professional activity, its economic and financial standing and to its technical and professional ability to perform the contract. They relate, for example to the previous experience with the execution of similar contracts, or to the availability of qualified personnel or of equipment needed to execute the contract. The selection criteria will be applied to the tenderers who have not been excluded on the basis of the previously discussed exclusion grounds.

(...) For PCP, the selection criteria should be formulated in compliance with the Treaty principles. This comes down to the same legal requirements as outlined for PPI. From a practical point of view, the procurer should avoid using disproportionate qualification, economic or financial guarantee requirements. For example, the procurer should not formulate requirements related to the economic standing of the provider (such as minimum turnover requirements) or past performance requirements (as PCP focuses on the development of new solutions that have not been tried by previous clients). Instead, the public procurer should focus on the capability of the economic operator to perform R&D and exploit R&D results.”

Source: EAFIP, Module 2, pp. 94-95.

3.4 Award criteria

There are 2 types of award criteria (on/off criteria and weighted criteria).

On/off award criteria

Explain that these are criteria that can only have value 0 or 1 and the score of the other award criteria must be multiplied by this value (so that the total score becomes 0 if a tender scores 0 on an on-off award criterion).

List the on/off criteria and the evidence to be provided. Explain that the offers for each phase will be evaluated against these criteria.

Tenders must comply with the following on/off award criteria:

On/off award criteria	Evidence
A) Compliance with the definition of R&D services	
B) Compatibility with other public financing	
C) Compliance with the requirements regarding the place of performance of the contract	
D) Compliance with ethics requirements	
E) Compliance with security requirements	
Additional on/off award criteria for the call-off for phase 2	
X) ...	
Additional on/off award criteria for the call-off for phase 3	
X) ...	

⚠ Tenders that do not comply with these criteria will be excluded.

[Explain each on/off criterion in more detail:](#)

A) Compliance with the definition of R&D services

Tenders that go beyond the provision of R&D services will be excluded.

R&D covers fundamental research, industrial research and experimental development, as per the definition given in the [EU R&D&I state aid framework](#)¹⁴. It may include exploration and design of solutions and prototyping up to the original development of a limited volume of first products or services in the form of a test series. Original development of a first product or service may include limited production or supply in order to incorporate the results of field-testing and to demonstrate that the product or service is suitable for production or supply in quantity to acceptable quality standards.¹⁵ R&D does not include quantity production or supply to establish commercial viability or to recover R&D costs. It also excludes commercial development activities such as incremental adaptations or routine or periodic changes to existing products, services, production lines, processes or other operations in progress, even if such changes may constitute improvements. The purchase of commercial volumes of products or services is not permitted.

The definition of services means that the value of the total amount of products covered by the contract must be less than 50 % of the total value of the PCP framework agreement.

[Specify the evidence to be provided to demonstrate compliance with this criterion.](#)

¹⁴ See Point 15 of the [Commission Communication on a framework for state aid for research and development and innovation](#) (C(2014) 3282).

¹⁵ See Article XV(1)(e) [WTO GPA 1994](#) and the Article XIII(1)(f) of the [revised WTO GPA 2014](#).

The following evidence is required:

- the financial part of the offer for the framework agreement must provide binding unit prices for all foreseeable items for the duration of the whole framework agreement
- the financial part of the offer for each phase must give a breakdown of the price for that phase in terms of units and unit prices for every type of item in the contract, distinguishing clearly the units and unit prices for items that concern products
- the offers for all 3 phases may include only items needed to address the challenge in question and to deliver the R&D services described in the request for tenders
- the offers for all 3 phases must offer services matching the R&D definition above
- the total value of products offered in phase 1 respectively phase 2 must be less than 50 % of the value of the phase 1 respectively phase 2 contract and the total value of products offered in phase 3 must be so that the total value of products offered in all phases (1,2 and 3) is less than 50% of the total value of the PCP framework agreement.
- ...

Both percentages for the product value inside phase 1 and phase 2 must be set at less than 50 % to ensure that tenders that do not go through to phase 2 or 3 still satisfy the definition of an R&D services contract.

B) Compatibility with other public financing

Tenders that receive public funding from other sources will be excluded if this leads to double public financing or an accumulation of different types of public financing that is not permitted by EU legislation, *including EU state aid rules*.

Specify the evidence to be provided to demonstrate compliance with this criterion. Require for example a declaration of honour for absence of other incompatible public financing.

C) Compliance with requirements relating to the place of performance of the contract

Tenders will be excluded if they do not meet the following requirements relating to the place of performance of the contract:

- at least [add percentage — if the PCP is funded by H2020 the minimum is 50 %] of the total value of activities covered by each specific contract for PCP phase 1 and 2 must be performed in the EU Member States *and/or, if funded, in H2020 associated countries*.
- at least [add percentage — if the PCP is funded by H2020 the minimum is 50 %] of the total value of activities covered by the framework agreement (*i.e. the total value of the activities covered by phase 1 + the total value of the activities covered by phase 2 + the total value of the activities covered by phase 3*) must be performed in the EU Member States *and/or, if funded, H2020 associated countries*.

[If funded by H2020: Both percentages for phase 1 and phase 2 must be set at a minimum of 50 % to ensure that tenders that do not go through to phase 2 or 3 still satisfy the place

of performance requirement. The countries associated to Horizon 2020 are those listed as associated countries in the Funding & Tenders Portal [Online Manual](#)^{16]}

Please note that the percentage is calculated as the part of the total monetary value of the contract that is allocated to activities performed in the EU Member States *and/or [if funded by H2020] in other countries associated to Horizon 2020*. All activities covered by the contract are included in the calculation (i.e. all R&D and operational activities that are needed to perform the R&D services, e.g. research, development, testing and certifying solutions). This includes all activities performed under the contract by contractors and, if applicable, their subcontractors.

[If funded by H2020: The principal R&D staff working on each specific contract could/must be located in the EU Member States or H2020 associated countries. The principal R&D staff are the main researchers, developers and testers responsible for leading the R&D activities covered by the contract].

Specify the evidence to be provided to demonstrate compliance with this criterion:

The following evidence is required:

- the financial part of the offer must provide binding unit prices for all foreseeable items for the duration of the whole framework agreement and give a breakdown of the price for the current phase in terms of units and unit prices (*hours and unit price per hour*), for every type of item in the contract (*e.g. junior and senior researchers*)
- a list of staff working on the specific contract (*including for subcontractors*), indicating clearly their role in performing the contract (*i.e. whether they are principal R&D staff or not*) and the location (*country*) where they will carry out their tasks under the contract
- a confirmation or declaration of honour that, where certain activities forming part of the contract are subcontracted, subcontractors will be required to comply with the place of performance obligation to ensure that the minimum percentage of the total amount of activities that has to be performed in the EU Member States or in countries participating in Horizon 2020 is respected
- ...

D) Ethics and research integrity

Tenders will be excluded if they:

- do not comply with the following rules:
 - ethical principles (*including the highest standards of research integrity, notably as set out in the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)¹⁸, and, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism and other research misconduct*)
 - applicable international, EU and national law
- include plans to carry out activities in a country outside the EU if they are prohibited in all Member States or plans to destroy human embryos

¹⁶ [List of H2020 associated countries.](#)

¹⁸ The [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) of ALLEA (All European Academies).

- include activities whose aim is to:
 - carry out human cloning for reproductive purposes
 - modify the genetic heritage of human beings in such a way as could make such changes heritable (with the exception of research relating to cancer treatment of the gonads)
 - create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, *including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer*
- include activities that do not focus exclusively on civil applications
- *[OPTION if H2020 grant agreement contains ethics requirements that affect the PCP contracts: do not comply with the following ethics requirements:*
 - *[insert the ethics deliverables from Annex 1 to the EU grant agreement]*.

If the tender involves activities that raise ethical issues, the tenderer must submit an ethics self-assessment that:

- describes how the tender meets the legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks raising ethical issues are to be carried out
- explains in detail how the tenderer intends to address the ethical issues identified, in particular as regards:
 - objectives (e.g. dealing with vulnerable populations and dual-use goods¹⁹)
 - methodology (e.g. involvement of children and related consent procedure and protection of data collected)
 - the potential impact (e.g. issues relating to the dual use of goods, environmental damage, stigmatisation of particular social groups, political or financial retaliation, benefit-sharing and malevolent use of results).

① For information on ethics issues, see the guidance for EU grant beneficiaries [How to complete your ethics self-assessment](#).

⚠ Attention:

Call-offs for phases 2 and 3 may request that this information be updated in the offers submitted for these phases.

Before starting the particular task that raises ethical issues, contractors must provide a copy of:

- any ethics committee opinion required under national law; and
- any notification or authorisation for activities raising ethical issues required under national law.

The framework agreement contains a provision on ethics.

E) Security

Tenders will be excluded if they do not:

¹⁹ See Article 2(1) EU Export Control Regulation No [428/2009](#).

- comply with:
 - EU, national and international law on dual-use goods or dangerous materials and substances
 - *[OPTION if H2020 grant agreement provides for a security classification that affects the PCP contracts: the security aspect letter (SAL) annexed to the H2020 grant agreement and Decision No [2015/444](#)²⁰]*
 - *[OPTION if H2020 grant agreement contains security recommendations that affect the PCP contracts: the following security recommendations:*
 - *[insert the security recommendations from Annex 1 to the H2020 grant agreement]*

Tenders themselves must not contain any classified information.

If the output of activities or results proposed in the tender raise security issues or uses EU-classified information, the tenderer must show that these issues are being handled correctly. In such a case, tenderers are required to ensure and to provide evidence of the adequate clearance of all relevant facilities. They must examine any issues (*such as those relating to access to classified information or export or transfer control*) with the national authorities before submitting their offer. Tenders must include a draft security classification guide (SCG), indicating the expected levels of security classification.

⚠ Attention:

If necessary, for the tender procedure or for performing the contract itself, contractors will be requested to ensure appropriate security clearance for third parties (*e.g. for personnel*).

Call-offs for phases 2 and 3 may request that this security information be updated in the offers submitted for that phase.

Before starting the particular task that raises security issues, contractors must provide a copy of any export or transfer licences required under EU, national or international law.

The framework agreement and/or the specific contracts contain a provision on security.

① For information on security, see *the guidance for EU grant beneficiaries: [Guidelines for the handling of classified information in EU research projects](#)*.

F)...

⚠ Attention: Should there be any doubt as to any of these criteria, tenderers may be requested to provide additional information.

Weighted award criteria

Specify the award criteria (and sub-criteria, where applicable), weightings and thresholds for each of the 3 phases (*solution design, prototyping, original development and testing of a limited set of 'first' products or services*):

Weighted award criteria	Maximum points	Thresholds	Weighting
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²⁰ Commission [Decision 2015/444/EC, Euratom](#) of 13 March 2015 on the security rules for protecting EU classified information

Phase 1: Solution design			
Technical quality criteria			
A) [insert technical quality criterion 1]			
B) [insert technical quality criterion 2]			
C) [insert technical quality criterion 3]			
D)...			
Total technical quality criteria			
Price			
Phase 2: Prototyping			
Technical quality criteria			
A) [insert technical quality criterion 1]			
B) [insert technical quality criterion 2]			
C) [insert technical quality criterion 3]			
D)...			
Total technical quality criteria			
Price			
Phase 3: Development & testing			
Technical quality criteria			
A) [insert technical quality criterion 1]			
B) [insert technical quality criterion 2]			
C) [insert technical quality criterion 3]			
D)...			
Total technical quality criteria			
Price			

Explain each weighted award criterion in more detail:

A) ...

B)...

⚠ Attention:

Additional sub-criteria may be added for the call-offs for phases 2 and 3, as a way of making the award criteria more precise, provided that they do not substantially change the existing criteria.

Should there be any doubt as to any of these criteria, tenderers may be requested to provide additional information.

Note:

The weighted award criteria must ensure that the procurer gets the best value for money. It is therefore not permitted to use either lowest price as the sole criteria, without taking quality into account, or highest quality as the sole criteria, without taking price into account.

Set the technical quality and price award criteria, weightings and thresholds so as to favour the most economically advantageous tenders. Define the thresholds per criterion and the total threshold.

Pay particular attention to the weighting given to price. It should be sufficiently high to avoid this criteria being neutralised in the evaluation. *(For example, a weighting of less than 20 out of 100 for price is too low for it to have a significant effect on the result.)*

State clearly whether all the award criteria will be evaluated by examining the written tender or whether some award criteria will be evaluated on the basis of hearings with or presentations to the evaluation committee.

LEARN MORE

Award criteria

“In compliance with the Treaty principles of equal treatment and transparency, the award criteria and the relative weightings of the award criteria should be published in advance in the tender documents, unless for objective reasons, this is not possible. In case of such impossibility, the public procurer shall indicate the criteria in descending order of importance.

For PCP projects, the award criteria should not be based on best quality only, but also on price.

When the procurer wants to apply different award criteria for each PCP Phase, it needs to specify the award criteria for each phase and their relative weightings upfront in the tender documents. The award criteria will be applied at each PCP Phase, when selecting the providers that will move to the next Phase.

(...) In order to remove unnecessary barriers for innovative new companies, typically SMEs, to make offers for the PCP call for tender, procurers should avoid the use of selection criteria based on stringent qualification requirements and disproportionate financial guarantee requirements (e.g. with regards to prior customer references and minimum turnover). As an alternative, procurers can consider including 'feasibility of the business-

case/commercialization plan' as award or as sub-award criterion in the evaluation of offers for every PCP phase (possibly with a gradually increasing weight factor across the different PCP phases): this approach requires participating companies to demonstrate that they are able to build up - gradually throughout the PCP process - sufficient financial capacity to successfully commercialise the solutions developed during the PCP.

Regarding the price criterion, it is recommendable to set up front a maximum price that may be offered by a tenderer (see example below). This prevents that the PCP will run out of budget and gives a clear indication to vendors also of the expected R&D effort for each PCP phase. In order to ensure that only offers with a minimum level of quality will be selected, the public procurer has the option to define a threshold, a minimum level of points that an offer has to reach on the qualitative criteria, in order to be awarded a contract (e.g. a minimum of 200 points, equivalent to 50-60 per cent of the total score)."

Source: EAFIP, Module 2, pp. 97-100.

Italy

According to Italian legislation, in case of service contracts and supplies for an amount equal to or greater than € 40,000 characterized by significant technological content or which have an innovative character, the contracting authority should adopt the MEAT criterion. The price element should be evaluated within the limit of 30% (Legislative Decree n. 50 of 18 April 2016, art. 95(10-bis)²¹.

²¹ This legal provision is under revision, based on Legislative Decree n. 32/2019 "**Unblock building sites**", as converted in L.55/2019 .

FINLAND

In accordance with section 93 of Act on Public Procurement and Concession Contract, the use of MEAT criterion is especially encouraged in procurements of works and services, so other than procurement of goods.

(1) The most economically advantageous tender shall be selected. The most economically advantageous tender shall be a tender at the lowest price, at the most affordable cost, or with the best price-quality ratio for the contracting entity. A contracting entity that, other than in procurements of goods, applies the lowest price as the sole criterion for determining the most economically advantageous tender shall set out the justifications for doing so in the procurement documents, in the procurement decision, or in a separate statement on the procurement procedure.

(2) The contracting entity may impose price-quality ratio comparison criteria related to qualitative, societal, environmental or social considerations or innovative characteristics. Qualitative criteria may include technical merits, aesthetic and functional characteristics, accessibility, a design that meets the requirements of all users, operating costs, cost-effectiveness, after-sales service and technical support, servicing and delivery date, or delivery or implementation period and other terms and conditions of delivery. The contracting entity may also consider the qualifications and experience of staff assigned to implement the procurement agreement and the organisation of staff if the quality of assigned staff may significantly affect implementation of the procurement agreement.

3) The contracting entity may also set out price-quality ratio cost factors in the form of a fixed price or costs, in which case the tenderers shall compete solely on quality-related grounds.

4) The contracting entity shall indicate the criterion for determining the most economically advantageous tender or the price-quality ratio comparison criteria that it employs in the contract notice, the call for tenders or the invitation to negotiate. The contracting entity shall specify the relative weighting of comparison criteria in the contract notice, the invitation to negotiate, or the call for tenders. The weighting may also be expressed by indicating a reasonable range. If no relative weighting of comparison criteria can be specified for objective reasons, then the comparison criteria shall be indicated in decreasing order of importance.

(5) The comparison criteria shall be linked to the procurement in accordance with section 94, they shall not afford the contracting entity unlimited freedom of choice, and they shall be non-discriminatory and ensure the possibility of genuine competition. The contracting entity shall impose the comparison criteria in a manner that enables a tenderer to verify the information based on them for the purpose of comparing tenders. The contracting entity shall effectively verify the accuracy of the information and proof provided by the tenderers in unclear cases.

Portugal

According to art. 74 of the CCP, the award shall be made according to one of the following criteria:

- (a) the most economically advantageous tender for the contracting authority;
- (b) the lowest price.

It is ruled that the lowest price criterion could be adopted when the specifications define all aspects of the contract, only by submitting to competition the price to be payable for the execution of all the subject-matter of the contract.

According to legislation in Portugal, when launching the tenders, it is mandatory to have the model of proposal evaluation, according to article 139 of the CCP. This model states that:

- If the most economically advantageous tender is determined by the price-quality ratio, or if the price or cost evaluation is broken down into more than one evaluation factor, the proposal evaluation model must comply with the provisions of the following paragraphs
- The overall score of each proposal expressed numerically corresponds to the result of the sum of the partial scores obtained in each elementary factor or subfactor, multiplied by the values of the respective weighting coefficients
- For each elementary factor or subfactor, a scoring scale must be defined by means of a mathematical expression or by an ordered set of different attributes that may be proposed for the performance aspect of the contract submitted to the competition by the specifications relating to that factor or subfactor.
- In the preparation of the proposal evaluation model, no data can be used that depend, directly or indirectly, on the attributes of the proposals to be presented, with the exception of those of the proposal to be evaluated.

the partial scores of each proposal shall be assigned by the jury through the application of the mathematical expression referred to in paragraph 3 or, if this does not exist, by means of a judgment comparing the respective attribute with the ordered set referred to in the same number

SPAIN

Article 145. "Requirements and kinds of contract award criteria" of the Law of Public Sector Contracts (Law 9/2017, November 8th)

1. Contracts will be awarded using a plurality of award criteria based on the best value for money.

Upon justification in the file, contracts may be awarded according to criteria based on an approach that meets the best cost-effectiveness, based on price or cost, such as the calculation of the life cycle cost according to the article 148.

2. The best value for money will be evaluated according to economic and qualitative criteria.

The qualitative criteria established by the contracting authority to evaluate the best value for money may include environmental or social aspects, linked to the object of the contract in the manner established in section 6 of this article, which may be, among others, the following:

1st. Quality, including technical value, aesthetic and functional characteristics, accessibility, universal design or design for all users, social, environmental and innovative characteristics, and marketing and its conditions;

The environmental characteristics may refer, among others, to the reduction of the emission level of greenhouse gases; the use of energy saving and efficiency measures and the use of energy from renewable sources during the execution of the contract; and to the

maintenance or improvement of natural resources that may be affected by the execution of the contract.

The social characteristics of the contract will refer, among others, to the following purposes: the promotion of social integration of persons with disabilities, disadvantaged persons or members of vulnerable groups among the persons assigned to the execution of the contract and, in general, the insertion socio-labor of persons with disabilities or in situation or risk of social exclusion; outsourcing with Special Employment Centers or Insertion Companies; gender equality plans that are applied in the execution of the contract and, in general, equality between women and men; the promotion of female hiring; the reconciliation of work, personal and family life; the improvement of working and salary conditions; job stability; the hiring of a greater number of people for the execution of the contract; training and protection of health and safety at work; the application of ethical and social responsibility criteria to the contractual provision; or the criteria related to the supply or use of products based on fair trade during the execution of the contract.

2nd. The organization, qualification and experience of the personnel assigned to the contract that will execute the same, as long as the quality of said personnel can significantly affect their best performance.

3rd. The after-sales service and technical assistance and delivery conditions such as the date on which the latter must be produced, the delivery process, the delivery or execution period and the commitments regarding spare parts and security of supply.

The qualitative criteria must be accompanied by a criterion related to costs which, at the choice of the contracting authority, may be the price or an approach based on profitability, such as the cost of the life cycle calculated in accordance with the provisions of the Article 148.

3. The application of more than one award criteria will proceed, in any case, in the award of the following contracts:

a) Those whose projects or budgets have not been previously established and must be presented by the candidates or bidders.

b) When the contracting authority considers that the definition of the object of the contract is likely to be improved by other technical solutions or by reductions in its execution period.

c) Those for whose execution the contracting body, organism or entity provides materials or auxiliary means whose good use requires special guarantees from the contractors.

d) Those that require the use of especially advanced technology or whose execution is particularly complex.

e) Contracts for the concession of works and the concession of services.

f) Supply contracts, unless the products to be acquired are perfectly defined and it is not possible to vary the delivery times or introduce modifications of any kind in the contract, being therefore the price the only determining factor of the award.

g) Service contracts, unless the benefits are perfectly defined technically and it is not possible to vary the delivery times or introduce modifications of any kind in the contract, being therefore the price the only determining factor of the award.

In service contracts that are intended to provide an intellectual object, such as engineering and architecture services, and in social service provision contracts if they encourage social integration of disadvantaged persons or members of vulnerable groups among persons assigned to the execution of the contract, promote the employment of people with

particular difficulties of insertion in the labor market or in the case of social, health or educational services contracts referred to in the forty-eighth additional provision, or labor-intensive services, the price may not be the sole determining factor of the award. Similarly, in the case of private security service contracts, more than one award criteria must be applied.

h) Contracts whose execution may have a significant impact on the environment, whose award will be assessed measurable environmental conditions, such as lower environmental impact, saving and efficient use of water and energy and materials, environmental cost of the life cycle, the procedures and methods of ecological production, the generation and management of waste or the use of recycled or reused materials or ecological materials.

4. The contracting bodies shall ensure that award criteria are established that allow obtaining high-quality works, supplies and services that best meet their needs; and, especially, in the procedures of service contracts that are intended to provide intellectual object, such as engineering and architecture services.

In the contracts of services of Annex IV, as well as in the contracts that are intended for intellectual benefits, the criteria related to quality must represent at least 51 percent of the assignable score in the valuation of the offers, without prejudice to the provisions of paragraph 2 (a) of article 146.

3.5 Evaluation procedure: Opening of tenders & evaluation

Opening of tenders

Describe the composition of the opening committee, *i.e. the number and type of members, without giving their names.*

Specify which points will be checked during the opening of tenders, in particular in relation to compliance with the conditions on the content and format of the offer (see above).

State that tenders not complying with the formal requirements will be excluded from the tender evaluation.

Give the date for the opening of the tenders and explain how tenderers can participate.

For phases 2 and 3, explain any differences in the composition of the opening committee or in the procedure.

Evaluation

Describe the composition of the evaluation committee (and its panels, where applicable), *i.e. specify:*

- *whether the evaluation committee is the same as the opening committee*
- *the number and type of members, without giving their names*
- *whether, in addition to the lead procurer and buyers group, there will be independent experts on the committee (e.g. technical experts on the subject, financial experts for evaluating the commercial viability of the solutions proposed or ethical or security experts).*

The evaluation committee will evaluate the tenders, carrying out the following four steps:

- Step 1 — Checking whether the tenderer is not in one of the situations covered by the exclusion criteria
- Step 2 — For tenderers passing Step 1, assessing whether the tenderer has the capacities necessary to perform the contract, on the basis of the selection criteria
- Step 3 — For tenderers passing Step 2, evaluating the tender based on the on/off award criteria
- Step 4 — For tenders passing Step 3, evaluating the tender based on the weighted award criteria

Explain the tasks of the chair and the members (and the different panels, where applicable).

Specify which members will be involved in the different steps of the evaluation.

Describe how the committee (and its panels) will work (e.g. when and how they will meet), and explain the process to be used for making decisions at each of the different steps (e.g. decision by unanimity).

Explain the system for scoring, qualitative appraisal and ranking (e.g. starting from a first round of individual evaluations and concluding with a final agreed qualitative appraisal; the scoring for each tender and the final ranking list of all tenders agreed by the lead procurer and buyers group).

Specify the type of feedback tenderers will receive from the evaluation of their tender.

For phases 2 and 3, explain any differences in the composition of the evaluation committee or in the procedure (Highlight in particular that the evaluation of offers for phase 2 has only 2 steps: evaluating the offers based on the on/off and weighted award criteria.)

Note:

For joint PCP, the buyers group and lead procurer must evaluate the tenders and offers for the call-offs for phase 2 and 3 *jointly* and must make a *joint* award decision. For coordinated PCP, each procurer carries out an *individual* evaluation and makes an *individual* award decision for the procurement that he carries out individually (based on the same common tender specifications established by all procurers in the buyer's group).

Avoid potential conflicts of interest.

 In case of PCP funded by H2020: for each phase and each tender received, the evaluation documents must be submitted as deliverable under the H2020 grant agreement — at the end of the tender evaluation. (They should include: the final scores awarded, a qualitative appraisal per evaluation criterion, minutes of the evaluation meeting and the final ranking list).

ITALY

For the purpose of the evaluation of the received tenderers, the Lead Procurer/the buyer's group shall appoint the following Evaluation Committees:

- a) An Administrative Committee for the selection of tenders based on exclusion and selection criteria. The administrative committee will be composed of 3 assessors.

Assessors shall open tenders. Only tenders that satisfy the provided requirements, which means that are not excluded based on the exclusion criteria and that meet the selection criteria, shall be considered admissible for evaluation under the weighted award criteria.

- b) Technical Evaluation Committee for the evaluation of tenders-based award criteria and the financial tender. The committee shall be composed of 3 or 5 evaluators appointed by the buyer's group who are experts in the specific field covered by the scope of the contract.

In order to guarantee fairness and transparency, the evaluator's appointment and the establishment of the Evaluation Committees shall take place after the expiry of the deadline for the submission of tenders.

Members of the Evaluation Committees nominated or designated by the Lead Procurer and the Procurers shall be appointed ad personam. When carrying out their tasks, they shall not seek or take instructions from the Lead Procurer institutions, bodies, offices or agencies, from any government of a Procurer or from any other body.

The Procurers undertake to respect this principle and not seek to influence the members of the Evaluation Committees in the performance of their tasks.

Each member of the Evaluation Committees shall sign the Declaration of the absence of conflict of interest and protection of confidentiality.

FINLAND

For the purpose of the evaluation of the received tenderers, the Act on Public Procurement and Concession Contract don't provide specific rules related to the organizational model and operational functioning of the evaluation committee.

PORTUGAL

According to the CCP, relevant articles describing the organizational model and process for proposal evaluations, are 67 and 69.

Jury (article 67)

1 - Except for the direct adjustment and the cases provided for in paragraph 3, the procedures for the formation of contracts shall be conducted by a jury, designated by the body responsible for the contracting decision, composed, in an odd number, for a minimum of three effective members, one of whom chairs, and two alternates.

2 - The members of the body competent for the decision to contract may be appointed members of the jury.

3. In the case of prior consultation or an urgent public procedure, the body responsible for deciding to contract may decide that the procedures are to be conducted by the contracting authority, considering the references made in this Code to the jury.

4 - The jury may be waived in procedures where only one proposal is submitted.

5 - Prior to the commencement of their functions, the members of the jury and all other parties involved in the tender evaluation process, including experts, shall sign a declaration that there is no conflict of interest, in accordance with the model set out in Annex XIII to this Code and which forms part of it integral.

Procedure (article 68)

1 - The jury of the procedure begins the exercise of its functions on the business day subsequent to the sending of the announcement for publication or the invitation.

2 - The jury can only work when the number of members present in the meeting corresponds to the number of effective members.

3 - The deliberations of the jury, which must always be based, are taken by majority vote, and abstention is not allowed.

4 - In the deliberations in which there is a defeated vote of a member of the jury, the minutes must be stated in the minutes for their dissent.

5 - The selection board may appoint a secretary from among the staff of the contracting authority, with the approval of the highest executive officer.

6 - When it considers it appropriate, the body competent for the decision to contract may appoint experts or consultants to support the selection board in the exercise of its functions, and may participate, without voting rights, in the meetings of the jury.

Jury responsibilities (article 69°)

1 - It shall be the responsibility of the jury:

a) To proceed with the evaluation of the applications;

b) to examine the proposals;

c) Evaluate solutions and projects;

d) Prepare the reports for the analysis of applications, proposals and solutions and projects.

2 - The jury shall also exercise the power delegated to it by the competent body for the decision to contract, but it may not delegate the power to rectify the parts of the procedure, the decision on errors or omissions identified by the interested parties, the decision on the qualification of candidates or the award decision.

SPAIN

2nd additional provision. Contracting competences for Local Entities.

7. The Evaluation Team of the contracting authority will be chaired by a member of the Corporation or an officer thereof, and will be part of it, as members, the Secretary or, where appropriate, the head of the body that has been assigned the function of legal advice, and the Financial Controller, or, as the case may be, the head of the body that has been assigned the function of economic-budgetary control, as well as those that are designated by the contracting body among the career civil servants or labor personnel in the service of the Corporation, or elected members thereof, without its number, in total, being less than three. The elected members who, where appropriate, are part of the Recruitment Board may not assume more than one third of the total members of the same. An official of the Corporation will act as Secretary.

In the local municipal Entities, associations and local consortiums, they may be integrated into the evaluation team personnel at the service of the corresponding Provincial Provinces or Uniprovincial Autonomous Communities.

In no case eventual personnel may be part of the Evaluation Teams or issue valuation reports of the offers, eventual personnel. Interim official staff may only be part of the Evaluation Team when there are insufficiently qualified career officials and this is proven in the file.

The composition of the Evaluation Team will be published in the contracting profile of the corresponding contracting authority. Permanent Contract Tables may be established.

8. The committee of experts referred to in letter a) of section 2 of article 146 of this Law, for the valuation of the criteria that depend on a value judgment, may be integrated in the local Entities by any official staff career or fixed employment with appropriate qualification that has not participated in the drafting of the technical documentation of the contract in question. In any case, among these personnel a legal technician specialized in public procurement must be included.

4. Content & format of tenders

4.1 Format

Explain the formal requirements that tenders must meet (*including the address for submission of the tender and requirements relating to the presentation of the offer and its packaging*).

State that all tenders must:

- contain administrative, technical and financial sections
- indicate their minimum validity period (from submission)
- be signed.

Specify that tenders that do not comply with the formal requirements will automatically be rejected.

Explain that more detailed information about the final layout requirements for the phase 2 and 3 offers will be provided in the call-off.

4.2 Administrative section

List the information that must be included in this section of the tender (*including the documentary evidence necessary to identify the tenderer and to evaluate the tender against the exclusion, selection and on/off award criterion B and — for joint tenders — the mandate for the lead contractor*).

Mention that the lead procurer may request clarification or additional evidence where there is any doubt.

Explain that more detailed information for the phase 2 and 3 offers will be provided in the call-offs.

4.3 Technical section

Explain what the technical section of the tender must include:

Tenders must include a **technical offer**, containing:

- a technical plan that outlines: 1. the tenderer's idea for addressing all the requirements given in the PCP challenge description, relating both to functionality and performance; and 2. technical details of how this would be implemented
- a draft business plan that explains the proposed approach to commercially exploit the results of the PCP and to bring a viable product or service onto the market
- a list of the pre-existing rights (*background*) relevant to the tenderer's proposed solution, in order to allow IPR dependencies to be assessed
- a risk assessment and risk mitigation strategy
- a reply to the question "Does this tender involve **ethical issues**? (YES/NO)" and if YES, an ethics self-assessment, with explanations how the ethical issues will be addressed
- a reply to the question "Does this tender involve: activities or results that may raise **security issues** and/or **EU-classified information**²² as background or results? (YES/NO)" and if YES information on how these issues will be addressed
- ...

 Attention:

Tenders failing to meet these requirements will be excluded.

The technical part must provide a *detailed* technical offer for phase 1 (*including an explanation of the methodology, a work plan and details of deliverables and milestones*), and must specify the plans for and objectives of the subsequent phases 2 and 3 and beyond (*including a plan for commercial exploitation of the results*).

Explain how the technical section of the tender should be drafted (possibly by providing a template).

State that the information provided in the technical section of the tender will be used to evaluate the tenders, on the basis of the technical award criteria and the on/off award criteria A, D and E.

Explain that more detailed information for the phase 2 and 3 offers (in particular on the technical implementation plan, updated business plan and list of IPRs) will be provided in the call-offs.

4.4 Financial section

Explain what the financial section of the tender must include:

The tender must include a detailed **financial offer** specifying:

- binding **unit prices** for all items needed for carrying out phase 1 and for items that are expected to be needed for phases 2 and 3 (*given in euros, excluding VAT but including any other taxes and duties*)
- a fixed **total price** for phase 1 and an estimated total price for phases 2 and 3, broken down to show unit prices and the number of each unit needed to carry out phase 1 (*given in euros, excluding VAT but including any other taxes and duties*).

In addition, the financial section must include:

²² See [Decision 2015/444/EC, Euratom](#) on the provisions on security of EU-classified information.

- a **price breakdown** that shows the price for R&D services and the price for supplies of products (to demonstrate compliance with the definition of R&D in on/off award criterion A)
- a **price breakdown** that shows the location or country in which the different categories of activities are to be carried out (e.g. *x hours of senior researchers in country L at y euro/hour; a hours of junior developers in country M at b euro/hour*) (to demonstrate compliance with the requirement relating to place of performance in on/off award criterion C)
- the **financial compensation** valuing the benefits and risks of the allocation of ownership of the **IPRs** to the contractor (i.e. *IPRs generated by the contractor during the PCP*), either:
 - *[OPTION if the procurers choose 'ex ante' valuation of the IPRs: by giving an absolute value for the price reduction between the price offered in the tender compared to the exclusive development price (i.e. the price that would have been quoted were IPR ownership to be transferred to the procurers)]*
 - *[OPTION if the procurers choose 'ex post' valuation of the IPRs: by confirming the tenderer's agreement with the chosen royalty scheme specified by the procurers, including the percentage of royalties that contractors will have to pay on sales/profits made from commercial exploitation of the IPRs]*

in order to ensure compliance with the [EU R&D&I state aid framework](#).

⚠ Attention: The unit prices quoted for each category of items (e.g. *hourly rates for junior and senior researchers, developers and testers*) remain binding for all phases (i.e. *for the duration of the framework agreement*).

Explain how the financial section of the tender should be written.

Explain whether and according to which formula unit prices can be indexed for phases 2 and 3.

Explain that the financial compensation for allocating IPR ownership to the contractor must reflect the market value of the benefits received (i.e. *the opportunity that the IPRs offer for commercial exploitation*) and the risks assumed by the contractor (e.g. *the cost of maintaining IPRs and bringing the products onto the market*). (Note that when the value of the risks equals or exceeds the value of the benefits, the financial compensation offered by vendors may be zero.)

State that the information provided in the financial section of the tender will be used to evaluate the tenders on the basis of the price award criteria and the on/off award criteria A and C.

Explain that more detailed information for the phase 2 and 3 offers will be provided in the call-off. The price for phase 2 and 3 offers must be based on the binding unit prices in the tender and the price conditions set out in the framework agreement. Where new units/unit prices (e.g. *for new tasks or equipment*) are subsequently added to the phase 2 or 3 offers, they will become binding for the remaining phases.

Similar price breakdowns will be requested for the call-offs for phase 2 and 3.

Note:

Indicate which VAT regime(s) apply. If all contractors will be paid by the lead procurer (*centralised payments*), it will be the VAT regime of the lead procurer. If the contractors

will be paid by each procurer in the buyers group individually (*pro rata to its contribution to the PCP procurement budget; decentralised payments*), it will be the VAT regime for each procurer for its share of the payment.

5. Miscellaneous

5.1 Language

All communication (relating to either the tender procedure or the implementation of the contract) must be carried out in English [or [add additional language(s), if any]].

Tenders as well as offers for phase 2 and 3 call-offs must be submitted in English [and [insert additional language(s), if any]].

Deliverables must be submitted in English [and [insert additional language(s), if any]].

Note:

Indicate specific language requirements, if necessary (for example, if certain tasks need to be carried out in cooperation with third parties locally, e.g. for field-testing with end-users who may speak only the local language).

5.2 Tender constitutes binding offer

A signed tender will be considered to constitute a firm, irrevocable, unchangeable and binding offer from the tenderer.

The signature of an authorised representative will be considered as the signature of the tender (and will be binding on the tenderer or, for joint tenders, the group of tenderers).

5.3 Unauthorized communication — Questions

The Q&A from the open market consultation can be found on [indicate the website where the Q&A from the open market consultation phase can be found].

For further questions, you may contact [the lead procurer via email and/or by other means] in English [and any additional languages chosen by the lead procurer and buyers group] until [insert date].

The summary of all questions and answers will be presented in an anonymised Q&A document that will be published on [indicate the website where the Q&A will be uploaded] in English [and any additional languages chosen by the lead procurer and buyers group] (final version planned for [insert date]). For phases 2 and 3, the answers will not be published, but distributed to all contractors that successfully completed the previous phase.

⚠ Attention: All other contacts (or attempted contacts) will be considered unauthorised and may lead to the exclusion of your tender.

5.4 Confidentiality

Tenderers must keep confidential any information obtained in the context of the tender procedure (including EU-classified information²³).

5.5 Contract implementation

Successful tenderers will be requested to sign both a framework agreement and specific contracts for phases 1, 2 and 3 (see the models given in Annexes 1 and 2).

Monitoring

During each phase, contract implementation will be monitored periodically and reviewed against the expected outcomes (*milestones, deliverables and output or results*) for the phase.

Each contractor will be assigned a main contact person (their supervisor) from the monitoring team appointed by the procurers.

There will be regular monitoring meetings between contractor and the supervisor/monitoring team.

Explain how often they will take place, how they will be conducted (physical meetings or remote/online meetings), and what they will involve. The contractors could be asked to discuss the results achieved in the preceding period and present their updated work plan; the monitoring team or supervisor could visit the contractor's premises to periodically monitor progress; the contractors could visit the procurer's premises (in particular at the start of a phase to get to know better the operational environment that solutions need to be designed for). Clarify that the contractor must cover its own costs and thus foresee personnel and travel budgets in its offer. In case of PCPs with lots, clarify if and when there will be meetings that involve contractors from the different lots to sort out dependencies between lots and to ensure that building blocks under development in different lots will ultimately work together as expected.

The monitoring team [or supervisor] will provide regular feedback to contractors after meetings or visits.

Explain how and when this will take place and how this will allow contractors to continuously improve the way in which their solutions address the problem set out in the PCP description.

Payments based on satisfactory completion of milestones and deliverables of the phase

Payments corresponding to each PCP phase will be subject to the *satisfactory* completion of the deliverables and milestones for that phase.

Satisfactory completion will be assessed by an assessment committee composed of [describe the composition of the assessment committee, without mentioning their names].

Satisfactory completion will be assessed according to the following requirements:

²³ Commission Decision [2015/444/EC, Euratom](#) of 13 March 2015 on the security rules for protecting EU-classified information.

- if the work corresponding to that milestone / deliverable has been carried out
- if a reasonable minimum quality has been delivered
- if the reports have been submitted on time
- if the monies have been allocated to the planned objectives
- if the monies have been allocated and the work has been carried out according to the on/off award criteria (place of performance, public funding and R&D definition criteria)

and

- if the work has been carried out in compliance with the provisions of the contract (*including in particular verification if the contractor has duly protected and managed IPRs generated in the respective phase*).

'Reasonable minimum quality' of a report means that:

- the report can be read by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert
- the report gives insight in the tasks performed in and the results
- the report is made using the end of phase report form or (if applicable) the milestone report form and the requirements of this form have been met
- ...

'Reasonable minimum quality' of a demonstration (for phase 2 or 3) means:

- the demonstration can be understood by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert (for instance, somebody with operational but not technical knowledge)
- the demonstration shows how the innovation works, how it can be used and (if applicable) how it is operated and maintained
- the demonstration is accessible to parties appointed by the procurers, unless these are direct competitors of the contractor
- ...

Satisfactory completion in each of the phases does not mean successful completion. (A PCP could, for instance, be satisfactorily completed even if it concludes that the innovation is not feasible.)

The assessment will consider the efforts made by contractors to take into account the feedback from the supervisor or the monitoring team.

Specify the terms of approval for deliverables (for reports and demonstrations respectively), in particular how many days the contractor has to approve/request modifications/reject deliverables, how many days the contractor has to resubmit deliverables.

Where the assessment committee judges the completion of deliverables or milestones to be unsatisfactory, [explain what happens, in particular the possible consequences in terms of reducing or withdrawing payments for that deliverable and/or terminating the contract].

Invoices must be submitted [to the lead procurer]/[pro-rata to each procurer in the buyers group].

[OPTION in case pro-rata payments are used: For every payment, the contractors must create [insert a number equal to the number of procurers in the buyers group] invoices which divide the amount according to the following distribution:

- [insert percentage that equals the ratio between the financial contribution of procurer X to the total PCP subcontracting cost (including the applicable VAT in country X) and the total PCP subcontracting cost (including VAT)] percent of the payment to be invoiced to [insert name of procurer X]]
- [...] percent of the payment to be invoiced to [insert name of procurer Y]]
- ...

Note: In an example of a buyers group with 3 procurers, each procurer must contribute the same amount (including VAT) to the total PCP subcontracting cost (i.e. for each payment 3 invoices equal to one third of the total payment amount; one invoice to each of the 3 procurers).]

Contractors' invoices must provide:

- a **price breakdown** showing the price for R&D services and the price for supplies of products (in order to demonstrate compliance with the definition of R&D in on/off award criterion A)
- a **price breakdown** showing the location or country in which the different categories of activities were performed (e.g. x hours of senior researchers in country L at y euro/hour, a hours of junior developers in country M at b euro/hour) (in order to demonstrate compliance with the requirement relating to the place of performance in on/off award criterion C).

Explain when payments will be made. Provide information on the amounts of the pre-instalments and interim payments (where applicable) and the payment of the balance.

Eligibility for the next phase based on successful completion of the phase

Eligibility for participation in the next phase will be subject to *successful* completion of the current phase.

Successful completion of a phase will be assessed by the assessment committee against the following requirements:

- if all milestones have been successfully completed
- if the R&D results meet the minimum functionality/performance requirements of the challenge description (i.e. the minimum quality/efficiency improvements which the procurers set forward for the innovative solutions to achieve)
- if the results of the R&D are considered to be promising
- ...

'Promising' means:

- for phase 1, that the feasibility is convincing
- for phase 2, that the feasibility, the applicability in an operational setting and the potential impact of the product is convincing

Note: There is a difference between satisfactory completion (requirement for payment) and successful completion (prerequisite for passing from one phase to the next).

Finalisation of phase 3: Possible follow-up PPI procurements

Follow-up PPI procurements for a *limited* set of prototypes and/or test products developed during this PCP procurement (*'limited follow-up PPIs'*) may be awarded by negotiated procedure (*with invitation to at least 3 potential providers, including those that successfully completed this PCP*).

Follow-up PPI procurements for a *commercial volume* of the innovative solutions developed in this PCP procurement will be subject to a new call for tenders.

If possible, please provide an indicative schedule for the procurement process that the buyers group would organise for deploying commercial volumes of the solutions, were the PCP to be completed successfully.

5.6 Cancellation of the tender procedure

The procurers may, at any moment, cease to proceed with the tender procedure and cancel it.

The procurers reserve the right not to award any contracts at the end of the tender procedure.

The procurers are not liable for any expense or loss the tenderers may have incurred in preparing their offer [, except for [insert if mandatory limits under national law]].

5.7 Procedures for appeal

Specify:

- the names of the appeal and mediation bodies foreseen under the national law applicable to the lead procurer and the time periods for filing a complaint and the different stages of dispute settlement.

Annex 1 - PCP Framework Agreement

Disclaimer: This model contract is aimed at assisting H2020 PCP grant beneficiaries. It is provided for information purposes only and is not intended to replace professional legal advice. It can be used as a starting point, but beneficiaries remain responsible for adapting it to their situation and checking compliance with the applicable law. Neither the European Commission nor its executive agencies and funding bodies (or any person acting on their behalf) can be held responsible for the use made of this model.

If funded and in order to comply with the conditions of the H2020 grant agreement, the framework agreements should contain at least the following elements/provisions:

PREAMBLE

This is a framework agreement ("Agreement" or "Framework Agreement") between the following parties:

on the one part,

the "lead procurer", [insert details of the lead procurer],

acting in the name and on behalf of the [other] procurers in the buyers group (together with the lead procurer: "procurers"):

1. [insert the details of the procurers in the buyers group (NOT of preferred partners or third giving in-kind contributions to the PCP!)]
- 2.

and on the other hand, the "contractor", [insert details of the contractor],

[OPTION for joint tenders: acting in the name and on behalf of the other members of group of tenderers:

1. [insert the details of the members of the group of tenderers]
- 2.

The members of the group of tenderers are hereafter collectively referred to as "the contractor" and will be jointly and severally liable vis-à-vis the lead procurer for the performance of this Framework Agreement and the Specific Contracts.]

The lead procurer, buyers group and the contractor(s) shall be referred to together as "parties", unless otherwise specified.

By signing this Agreement the parties agree to implement the pre-commercial procurement in accordance with the Agreement and all the obligations it sets out.

The Agreement is composed of:

- Preamble
- Terms and Conditions
- Annex 1 Request for tenders
- Annex 2 Contractor's tender

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

If funded and in order to comply with the conditions of the H2020, the framework agreements should contain at least the following provisions:

Article 1 — Subject of the agreement

This Framework Agreement defines the general terms and conditions for the implementation of the PCP procurement of R&D services set out in Article XX and for the Specific Contracts that will be awarded for each of the 3 PCP phases.

Article XX — Duration

Define the duration for the framework agreement and starting and end date for the implementation of the tasks.

Specify that the period of execution of the tasks may be extended only with the express written agreement of the parties before the expiration of the period for execution of the tasks.

Article XX — R&D services to be provided

The contractor shall provide the R&D services (tasks, deliverables and milestones) to develop solutions to tackle the challenge set out in the tender and the Specific Contracts.

Article XX — Pricing, payment and accounting

The price for the R&D services to be implemented for each PCP phase will be set out in the Specific Contracts.

The prices shall be based on the binding unit prices in the tender and the following price conditions:

- if new units/unit prices are added to phase 2 or 3 offers, they shall become binding for the remaining phases
- ... specify the other price conditions

Specify the payment and invoicing conditions that will apply. Ensure consistency with the request for tenders/tender (if needed via cross-references).

Article XX — Ownership of the results (foreground), pre-existing rights (background) and sideground (including intellectual and industrial property rights)

Include provisions that clarify the rights and obligations related to pre-existing rights (background), sideground and results (foreground) for:

- procurers,
- the contractor and
- its subcontractors (if any).

Provide **definitions**, notably for:

- 'results (*i.e. foreground*)' means any tangible or intangible output, such as data, knowledge or information, that is generated in the PCP, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights ('attached IPRs' or 'IPRs attached to the results')
- 'pre-existing rights (*i.e. background*)' means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any attached rights such as intellectual property rights ('background IPRs') — that is held prior to the signing of the framework agreement, identified by the parties involved in the PCP as background and needed to implement the PCP or exploit the results of the PCP
- 'sideground' means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any attached rights such as intellectual

property rights ('sideground IPRs') — that is generated during the timespan of the PCP but not in the PCP and needed to implement the PCP or to exploit the results of the PCP

- 'fair and reasonable conditions' means appropriate conditions, including financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access (for example, the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged)
- 'Generated in the PCP' means in activities described in the PCP framework agreement or specific contracts
- 'Not generated in the PCP' means not generated in activities described in the PCP framework agreement or specific contracts

Provide for the rights and obligations in relation to **results**. Specify:

- that each contractor that generates results **owns** the attached IPRs
- who will **own results that are not IPRs** (e.g. prototypes and first products resulting from the R&D, design, prototype and first product/service specifications, simulations, data models, drawings, source code)
- that each contractor is responsible for the **management** (including protection) of its IPRs and bears the costs associated with this
- that the procurers have the right to **monitor** the management of the IPRs
- that the contractor must inform the buyers group (via the lead procurer) of results that can be **exploited**, regardless of whether they can be protected or not, within [insert number] days from when they are generated. The information submitted to the lead procurer must include information about the contents of the results, the confirmation by the contractor to protect them and the planned timing for protection.
- that if a contractor does not seek **protection** for results that should be protected, the buyers group has the right to request (via the lead procurer) that the results are transferred to them
- that the contractor grants to the buyers group irrevocable, royalty-free, non-exclusive, world-wide **access** rights to use the results, for their own purposes (for IPRs: until their expiry date)
- that, for results that are an implementation of design specifications into simulations, prototypes, demonstrators or first products /services, those access rights are limited to a duration of [insert duration] years and to the following purposes for fulfilling the R&D objectives of the PCP: [specify those purposes for your PCP]
- that the EU and certain other third parties have special access rights
- that the buyers group has [the right to grant] [the right to require the contractor to grant — within a reasonable time period specified in the request —] **non-exclusive licences to third parties** to commercially or non-commercially exploit the results under fair and reasonable conditions, without the right to sub-license
- that the contractor may grant non-exclusive licences to third parties allowing them to exploit the results (or otherwise give the right to exploit them) — unless this impedes the access rights of the buyers group

- that the contractor may **transfer ownership** of its results — unless this is prohibited (or restricted) by the security obligations and provided that it ensures that its obligations (in respect of the results) apply to the new owner and that this new owner is obliged to pass them on in any subsequent transfer (e.g. by including a requirement to do so in their arrangements with the new owner)

You may foresee a right of first refusal for the buyers group to buy the results.

You should also foresee a procedure for transfers when there are procurers in the buyers group that still have (or may still request) access rights to the results (e.g. that the contractor must give them at least 45 days advance notice of its intention to transfer ownership of the results and that this notification must include sufficient information on the new owner to enable the procurers to assess the effects on their access rights. A procurer can object within 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that the transfer would adversely affect its access rights. Should an objection be raised, the transfer may not take place until agreement has been reached between the parties concerned).

- whether the contractor is required to **deposit copies** of results (e.g. the source code and design specifications), for example, under an ESCROW agreement designed to guarantee the buyers group continued access to results in the case of financial bankruptcy of the contractor (or any of its subcontractors).

Provide for the rights and obligations concerning **pre-existing rights** (background) and sideground. Specify:

- rules regarding **ownership** of pre-existing rights and sideground (normally remains unchanged)
- that the parties must inform each other about the generation of/changes in pre-existing rights and sideground within [insert number] days from the generation /change
- that the contractor introducing background must within [define period e.g. 2 weeks] of the signing of the PCP framework agreement provide the lead procurer with a **list of the pre-existing rights** it holds and/or has access to (e.g. via its subcontractors) (at the date of the agreement) and a list of the software necessary for the operation of the prototype and first [products]/[services] that will be developed during the PCP, specifying which software is closed source software. An updated list (to the extent necessary) must be provided with each bid for the next phase
- the **access** that the parties must grant each other to each other's pre-existing rights and sideground for carrying out the tasks assigned to them in the PCP, for exploitation of results generated in the PCP and for using the results for their own purposes (normally at least to the buyers group)

The conditions for access should be fair and reasonable to all parties, e.g. — if appropriate for your PCP —

- on a royalty-free, non-exclusive basis, access to each other's background, for carrying out the tasks assigned to them in the PCP
- under fair and reasonable conditions and on non-exclusive basis, access to each other's background, for exploitation of results generated in the PCP and for using the results for their own purposes

- *under fair and reasonable conditions and on non-exclusive basis, access to each other's sideground, for carrying out the tasks assigned to them in the PCP, for exploitation of results generated in the PCP and for using the results for their own purposes*

Note:

If funded and in If you use other definitions (allowed), make sure that they are compatible with your obligations under the H2020 grant agreement.

The limitation of the scope and duration of the access rights (to 'what is needed by the buyers group to fulfil the R&D objectives of the PCP') is needed for the PCP to remain an 'R&D procurement' where the 'procurers do not retain all the benefits' and thus be exempted from the WTO rules and the EU public procurement directives.

Don't forget to foresee:

- rules that define third party rights and obligations with respect to the above points on results, pre-existing rights and sideground (in the Article on participation of preferred partners and third parties providing in-kind contributions)
- rules on subcontractor rights and obligations with respect to the above points on results, pre-existing rights and sideground (*e.g. that the contractor must ensure that it complies with its obligations under the framework agreement and specific contracts if it uses subcontractors; that it must obtain all necessary rights (transfer, licences or other) from subcontractors, as if they were generated by itself; that it should refrain from using subcontractors if obtaining those rights is impossible*)

Third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP and preferred partners should be covered in the Article on participation of preferred partners and third parties providing in-kind contributions.

Do not forget to include the special IPR provisions from the H2020 grant agreement into the PPI contracts (*e.g. EU right to object to transfers or licencing of results; additional exploitation or dissemination obligations, access to research data etc*).

You may specify additional intellectual property provisions, provided they:

- do not conflict with the obligations under the H2020 grant agreement and
- help the procurers or the contractor to implement the PCP as well as disseminate and exploit the results.

Article XX — Confidentiality

The parties shall keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at the time it is disclosed. This applies during the implementation of the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts and up to [insert number of years (minimum 4 years after the end of the H2020 grant)] years after their end.

If information has been identified as confidential only orally, it shall be considered to be confidential only if this is confirmed in writing within 15 days of the oral disclosure.

The parties may disclose confidential information to their staff or to third parties involved in the PCP implementation only if:

- they need to be aware of this information in order to implement the PCP activities under the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts; and
- they are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

The procurers may disclose confidential information to the EU if required under their Horizon 2020 grant agreement.

The confidentiality obligations cease to apply if:

- (a) the disclosing party agrees to release the other party from the obligation;
- (b) the information was already known by the recipient or is given to him without obligation of confidentiality by a third party that was not bound by any obligation of confidentiality;
- (c) the recipient proves that the information was produced without the use of confidential information;
- (d) the information becomes generally and publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation; or
- (e) the disclosure of the information is required by EU or national law.

This does not change the security obligations, which still apply. Stricter confidentiality obligations apply for information that is EU-classified or subject to a security recommendation.

Article XX — Promotion, publicity and communication

XX.1 The contractor shall undertake communication activities to create publicity about its participation to the procurement, and to promote the objectives and the results of the R&D carried out under the PCP (*in particular to other potential customers with the objective to achieve commercial exploitation of the results; see Article XX – Commercial exploitation of results*).

All communication activities shall comply with the applicable confidentiality and security restrictions.

During the implementation of the contract and for a period of [insert number] [years]/[months] after the end of the contract, the contractor shall inform the lead procurer [indicate number] days in advance of any (written or oral) publication or any other type of communication (in any media or form) relating to the services or results. Information on communication activities expected to have a major media impact shall be provided sufficiently in advance to allow the lead procurer to inform the EU.

All communication activities (*including in electronic form and via social media*) and infrastructure, equipment and major results financed by the PCP shall display the EU emblem and include the following text:

- for communication activities: 'This is part of the [acronym of the H2020 grant] project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme';
- for infrastructure, equipment and major results: 'This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of the [acronym of H2020 grant] project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme'.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem shall have appropriate prominence. The contractor may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the EU. This does not, however, give the contractor the right to exclusive use. Moreover,

the contractor may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

All communication activities shall indicate that they reflect only the author's views.

XX.2 The procurers may use, for the purposes of communication and publicity, all information relating to the PCP, documents (*notably summaries*) and deliverables, and any other material (*such as pictures or audio-visual material*) from the contractor (*including in electronic form*).

The procurers may, in particular, publish the names of the participating contractor and its project abstracts, the summaries of the main results from the R&D and the lessons learnt during the PCP (*e.g. relating to the feasibility of the different approaches to meeting the procurers' requirements that were explored, and the lessons learnt for potential future use of the solutions proposed*).

This does not change the confidentiality obligations under Article XX.

Moreover, before publishing this information, the procurers shall consult the contractor, in order to avoid harm to legitimate business interests (*e.g. regarding aspects of the solutions that could be IPR-protected*) or distortion of competition.

XX.3 The EU may use, for the purposes of communication and publicity, information relating to the PCP, documents (*notably summaries*) and deliverables, and any other material (*such as pictures or audiovisual material*) from the contractor (*including in electronic form*).

If the EU's use of these materials, documents or information would risk compromising legitimate interests, the contractor may, however, ask the lead procurer to request the EU not to use it.

The right to use the contractor's materials, documents and information includes:

- (a) use for its own purposes (*in particular, making them available to staff working for the EU (including for the European Commission, EU executive agencies, other EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies) or for EU Member State institutions or bodies; and copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers*);
- (b) distribution to the public (*in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes*);
- (c) editing or redrafting for the purposes of communication and publicity (*including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (such as meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g. audio or video files), dividing into parts or using in a compilation*);
- (d) translation;
- (e) giving access in response to individual requests made under EU Regulation No 1049/2001²⁴, without the right to reproduce or exploit;
- (f) storage in paper, electronic or other form;

²⁴ Regulation (EC) No [1049/2001](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2001 regarding public access to European Parliament, Council and Commission documents, OJ L 145, 31.5.2001, p. 43.

- (g) archiving, in line with applicable rules on document management, and
- (h) authorising third parties to act on its behalf or sub-licensing the modes of use set out in points (b), (c), (d) and (f) to third parties if needed for the purposes of communication and publicity.

If the right of use is subject to rights of a third party (*including the contractor's staff*), the contractor shall ensure that it obtains the necessary approval from the third parties concerned.

Article XX — Commercial exploitation of results

The contractor shall, for at least [insert number of years (minimum 4 years after the end of the H2020 grant)] years after the end of the Framework Agreement and the Specific Contracts, take measures to ensure that its results are exploited commercially (directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing).

If the contractor fails to commercially exploit the results within this period (or uses the results to the detriment of the public interest, *including security interests*), the buyers group has the right to require that ownership of the results be transferred to them.

'Failure to commercially exploit results' means not marketing a commercial application of the results (directly or indirectly, through a subcontractor or licensee).

Note:

Set the period of time allowed in such a way as to give the contractor a fair and reasonable amount of time to exploit the results in the relevant sector. This will ensure that the potential for marketing the product or service is valued correctly (an appropriate length of time would typically be longer than 4 years, e.g. 5 years). The period should take account of the fact that: 1. the contractor needs to start producing the good or service in quantity and to invest in large scale promotion activities; and 2. the potential first customers, public procurers, generally take time to prepare and launch a PPI after the PCP has been completed.

Article XX — Conflicts of interest

XX.1 The contractor shall take all measures necessary to prevent a situation arising where the impartial and objective implementation of the Framework Agreement or a Specific Contract is compromised for reasons involving economic interests, political or national affinity, family, personal life or any other shared interest.

The contractor shall also take all measures necessary to prevent a situation in which its (previous or ongoing) professional activities affect the impartial and objective implementation of the Framework Agreement or a Specific Contract.

XX.2 The contractor shall notify the lead procurer without delay of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interest (*including changes of ownership*) and shall immediately take all steps necessary to rectify this situation.

The lead procurer may instruct the contractor to take specific measures to remedy the situation.

Article XX — Ethics and research integrity

XX.1 The contractor shall carry out the tasks assigned to it in the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts in compliance with:

- (a) ethical principles (*including the highest standards of research integrity*) and
- (b) applicable international, EU and national law.

The contractor may not:

- carry out activities in a country outside the EU, if they are prohibited in all EU Member States or
- destroy human embryos.

The contractor may not carry out activities whose aim is to:

- (a) carry out human cloning for reproductive purposes;
- (b) modify the genetic heritage of human beings in such a way as could make such changes heritable (with the exception of research relating to cancer treatment of the gonads) or
- (c) create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, *including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer*.

The contractor may not carry out activities that do not focus exclusively on civil applications.

The contractor shall respect the fundamental principle of research integrity — as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity²⁵.

This implies compliance with the following essential principles:

- **reliability** in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
- **honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way;
- **respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
- **accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts

This and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in this Code.

XX.2 Before starting any activity that raises an ethical issue, the contractor shall submit to the lead procurer a copy of:

- (a) any ethics committee opinion required under national law and
- (b) any notification or authorisation for activities raising ethical issues required under national law.

[OPTION if the H2020 grant agreement contains ethics requirements that concern the PCP contracts: XX.3 In addition, the contractor shall comply with the following ethics requirements:

²⁵ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA (All European Academies) and ESF (European Science Foundation) of March 2011.

http://www.esf.org/fileadmin/Public_documents/Publications/Code_Conduct_ResearchIntegrity.pdf

- [insert the ethics deliverables from Annex 1 to the H2020 grant agreement].]

Article XX — Security-related obligations

[OPTION if the contracts involve dual-use goods or dangerous materials or substances: XX.X Activities involving dual-use goods or dangerous materials and substances shall comply with applicable EU, national and international law.

Before starting the activity, the contractor shall provide the lead procurer with a copy of any export or transfer licences required.]

[OPTION if the H2020 grant agreement provides for a security classification that affects the PCP contracts: XX.X Classified information shall be treated in accordance with the security aspect letter (SAL) annexed to the H2020 grant agreement and EU Decision No 2015/544²⁶ until it is declassified.

Tasks involving classified information may not be subcontracted without prior written approval from the lead procurer.

The contractor shall inform the lead procurer of any changes relating to security and, if necessary, request an amendment.]

[OPTION if the H2020 grant agreement contains security recommendations restricting disclosure or dissemination that affect the PCP contracts: XX.X The following results may be disclosed or disseminated only if the contractor has first obtained written approval from the lead procurer:

- [insert the results subject to a security recommendation restricting disclosure or dissemination from Annex 1 to the H2020 grant agreement].]

[OPTION if the H2020 grant agreement contains other security recommendations that affect the PCP contracts: XX.X In addition, the contractor shall comply with the following security recommendations:

- [insert the security recommendations from Annex 1 to the H2020 grant agreement].]

Article XX — Processing of personal data

The contractor shall process personal data in compliance with the applicable EU and national law on data protection (*including as relates to authorisations and notification requirements*).

The contractor may grant its staff access to data only in so far as is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts.

The contractor must inform the staff whose personal data are collected and processed by the procurers and/or the EU. For this purpose, the contractor must provide them with the privacy statements of the procurers and the EU, before transmitting their data. If explicit prior consent from the data subjects is needed, the contractor must obtain such consent.

²⁶ Commission Decision [2015/444/EC, Euratom](#) of 13 March 2015 on the security rules for protecting EU-classified information.

Article XX — Obligation to provide information and keep records

XX.1 The contractor must, at any time during the implementation of the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts or afterwards, provide any information requested by the procurers in relation to the Agreement or Contracts.

XX.2 The contractor must keep, for a period of up to [insert number of years (minimum 5 years after the end of the H2020 grant agreement)] years after the end of the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts, records and other supporting documentation relating to their implementation.

This obligation includes records and other supporting documentation on scientific and technical implementation (in line with the accepted standards in the field) and on the price charged and the costs incurred by the contractor.

The contractor must keep the original documents. Digital and digitalised documents are considered originals if they are authorised under national law.

Should there be ongoing checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation or other pursuits of claims (*including claims by a third party against the procurers*), the contractor must keep all records and other supporting documentation until the end of these procedures.

Article XX — EU checks, reviews, audits and investigations

Should the EU (*including the European Court of Auditors or the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF)*) decide to carry out a check, review, audit or investigation, the contractor must make available all information, records and other supporting documents relating to the implementation of the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts.

Should there be an on-the-spot visit, the contractor must allow access to its premises and must ensure that the information requested is readily available.

Article XX — EU impact evaluation

Should the EU carry out an impact evaluation (of its grant to the procurers), the contractor must make available all information, records and other supporting documents relating to the implementation of the Framework Agreement and Specific Contracts.

Article XX — Breach of contract

Set out the consequences in case of breach of contract (in line with the law applicable to the contract).

Don't forget provisions on partial/improper implementation of tasks and breach of other obligations.

Include a section on liability for damages:

XX.1 The contractor must compensate the procurers if they are held liable by the EU for damage sustained as a result of the implementation of the Framework Agreement or a Specific Contract (or because it was not implemented properly).

XX.2 The EU cannot be held liable for any damage caused to the contractor or caused by the contractor in connection with the implementation of the Framework Agreement or a Specific Contract.

[OPTION in case there are preferred partners and third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP: Article XX — Participation of preferred partners and third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP)

Complete as applicable to the specificities of the PCP. Name the preferred partners and third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP and explain the boundary conditions for their participation, *i.e. the rights and responsibilities under the agreement and specific contracts.*

Pay particular attention to clearly set out the rules for participating in testing/monitoring/evaluation of results, confidentiality, processing of personal data and communication.

Specify also clearly the IPR-related rights (*e.g. access rights to results needed to follow the implementation of the PCP*) and obligations of preferred partners and third parties providing in-kind contributions to the PCP (*e.g. access rights to pre-existing rights, sideground or results (foreground) needed by contractors to implement the PCP or exploit its results*).]

Article XX — Amendments

Include a provision on amendments. Specify that they must be made in writing.

Include a clause that the amendment may not have the purpose or the effect of making changes to the contracts which might call into question the decision awarding the contracts or result in unequal treatment of tenderers.

Article XX — Interpretation

Include a provision specifying that the terms set out in the framework agreement have precedence over those in annexes and that the terms set out in Annex 1 (request for tenders) have precedence over those set out in Annex 2 (contractor's tender).

Specify that the same applies to the specific contracts.

Article XX — Applicable law and dispute settlement

Choose:

- *the law applicable to the framework agreement and to the specific contracts*
- *the dispute settlement mechanisms, in particular the competent court or other dispute settlement mechanisms (e.g. arbitration or mediation, if allowed under national law) and the deadlines to respect.*

Article XX — Entry into force

Define the entry into force (*e.g. upon signature of the last party*)

SIGNATURES

The lead procurer signs for the buyers group and — in case of joint tenders — the lead contractor for the group of contractors.

Annex 2 - PCP Specific contract for phase

PCP Specific contract for phase [1][2][3]

Disclaimer: This model contract is aimed at assisting H2020 PCP grant beneficiaries. It is provided for information purposes only and is not intended to replace professional legal advice. It can be used as a starting point, but beneficiaries remain responsible for adapting it to their situation and checking compliance with the applicable law. Neither the European Commission nor its executive agencies and funding bodies (or any person acting on their behalf) can be held responsible for the use made of this model.

Specific contracts must contain at least the following elements/provisions:

PREAMBLE

Similar set-up as the framework agreement: Lead procurer concludes and signs in in the name and on behalf of the buyers group.

Annex the contractor's offer.

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Article 1 — Subject of the contract

This Specific Contract defines the specific terms and conditions for the implementation of the PCP procurement of R&D services set out in Article XX — for the [1st][2nd][3rd] PCP phase.

Article XX — Duration

Specify the duration of the specific contract and starting and end date for the implementation of the tasks.

Specify that the period of execution of the tasks may be extended only with the express written agreement of the parties before the expiration of the period for execution of the tasks.

Article XX — R&D services to be provided

The contractor shall provide the R&D services (tasks, deliverables and milestones) set out in the offer for this phase.

Specify the scope of the specific contract (*i.e. which phase and which lot, if any*).

Specify the individuals in charge of carrying out the R&D activities for the specific contract and their location (country where they carry out the R&D activities).

Article XX — Price and payment arrangements

The price to be paid by [the lead procurer][the procurers in the buyers group] for the R&D services set out in Article XX shall be [EUR][other currency] [amount in figures and in words].

Specify the amounts of pre-instalments and interim payments (if applicable) and final payment in figures and words. In case of pro rata payments by the procurers in the buyers

group, split the amount pro rata per procurer according to their contribution to the total PCP subcontracting cost (with and without VAT).

Specify which invoice for which payment x the contractor has to send to whom (lead procurer or buyers group) after approval of deliverable x. Specify how many days after receipt of the invoice payment(s) have to be made to the contractor.

Specify the contractor's bank account details and the currency in which payments will be made.

Article XX — Security related obligations

Add a provision on security if specifically needed for the phase and not already covered by the provision in the framework agreement.

Article XX — Entry into force

Specify the entry into force date.

SIGNATURES

Same as for framework agreement: The lead procurer signs for the buyers group and — in case of joint tenders — the lead contractor for the group of contractors.

Annex 3 - Technical specification

Optional; needed for example if the PCP challenge is too long to describe in the request for tenders or if there is a need to add specifications describing how the solutions to be developed in the PCP need to interact with the other systems/products/services at the procurers premises)

Annex(es) 4 – Templates for administrative declarations concerning: exclusion, selection and on/off award criteria

If needed, e.g. declaration of honour for exclusion criteria, absence of conflict of interest and absence of incompatible other public financing.

Annex(es) 5 - Tender forms

Needed, it should include the forms for the technical and economic offers, at least for Phase 1 tendering.

Annex(es) 6 - Template for contractual deliverables

Recommended but Optional; only needed if the request for tenders does not specify the minimum information contractors are required to submit in the contractual deliverables as listed in the “Expected outcomes (per phase)” table at p.24.

